

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D5.6 Engagement activities reporting v2

WP5 - Engagement, change
management and sustainability

Version: 1.0

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Executive Summary

Deliverable *D5.6 - Engagement activities reporting v2* draws from its previous version D5.3, and conclude the reporting in regards to activities linked with two WP5 tasks: *T5.2 – Engaging with the innovation ecosystems* and *T5.3 – Raising awareness and engagement activities*. These tasks include the implementation of the dedicated engagement activities organised by the CALIPER seven RPOs and two RFOs, aimed at creating a favourable environment for the implementation and institutionalisation of their tailored and inclusive Gender Equality Plans. This deliverable covers the efforts and activities performed from M30 until M48 of the project. The main part of the reporting provided addresses the second and third rounds of awareness raising sessions that CALIPER PROs and RFOs have implemented. What is more, the deliverable also includes the reporting of IRB's WIN event as this was originally planned and presented in the previous deliverable, D5.3, but carried out afterwards.

This deliverable documents the completion of the project's activities that aim to disseminate the partners' GEPs and increase the engagement with their GEP actions of both internal and external stakeholders, as those have been envisioned through the action plan provided within WP5 relative tasks.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

A GEP should be actively communicated both internally and externally to increase awareness and engagement to the actions foreseen. Taking into consideration this fact, several communication and engagement actions are foreseen within the CALIPER's lifetime for ensuring internal and external commitment of key stakeholders that will in turn facilitate the implementation and the sustainability of the tailored GEP for each CALIPER partner.

This deliverable, D5.6, is the second and concluding version of the engagement activities reporting. The scope is to present those internal and external engagement activities/sessions organised by each CALIPER RPO/RFO until the finalisation of their relevant timeframe under tasks:

- T5.2 Engaging with the innovation ecosystems,
- T5.3 Raising awareness and engagement activities.

Primarily, the current deliverable provides reporting and documentation in regard to the second and third rounds of awareness raising sessions that have been planned and executed by each CALIPER RPO/RFO. On many occasions, the project partners opted to carry out such activities with additional relevant project efforts in order to proliferate the diffusion of CALIPER GEPs' vision and derived knowledge.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured in five chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the purpose and scope of the present deliverable along with its linkages with other WPs and Tasks. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the internal and external engagement activities that each RPO and RFO had to organise within the context of T5.2, T5.3 and T6.3, describing their purpose and objectives. Chapter 3 presents the implemented activities per RPO/RFO. Lastly, chapter 4 includes a few final remarks of the deliverable.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is part of *Task 5.3 – Raising awareness and engagement activities* of WP5 *Engagement, change management and sustainability*, aiming at presenting the results of the engagement activities, organised by the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs to disseminate their GEP internally and externally. This task is linked to *T5.2 – Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CALIPER Win Events*. T5.3 also contributes to WP6 – *Dissemination and communication*, and more specifically to *T6.2 – Intra-institutional internal communication*, and *T6.3 – External communication and multiplying effect*. These tasks are related due to the communication and dissemination activities they include. The D5.6 is also interlinked with *T1.3 – Methods and good practices on engendering research- innovation ecosystems*, *T1.4 – Analysis of external framework conditions and innovation ecosystems from a gender perspective GEPs* and *T2.2 - The organisation of Multi Stakeholder dialogues* since the reported activities draw information and resources based on the outputs of these tasks.

2 Overview and objectives of the internal and external engagement activities

This chapter gives a brief overview of the scope of each internal and external engagement activity that each partners had to organised up until now. These activities are:

1. The second and third rounds of the online raising awareness sessions (Part of T5.3)
2. The Women in Innovation – Win event (part of T5.2)

Overall, those activities aim at having **inward impact** by promoting structural changes for gender equality internally via engaging internal stakeholders for facilitating the institutionalization of your GEP activities and **outward impact by** expanding and promote the project results in the local innovation ecosystem via the involvement of the CALIPER R&I local Hubs.

2.1 Online awareness session

Within the *Task 5.3: Raising awareness and engagement activities* each GEP implementing partner must organise three rounds of online raising awareness sessions aimed at providing additional content to support the GEP Working Groups in raising internal awareness, increasing engagement throughout the different steps of the structural change process, and facilitating the change of the institutional culture based on gender equality, inclusion, and diversity. Three rounds of online raising awareness sessions are foreseen to be implemented in each RPO and RFO for going more in depth on facts, arguments, tools, and strategies to address each one of the three ERA objectives on gender equality, on which the CALIPER inclusive GEPs are contributing. The present deliverable focused on the first round of the online awareness sessions.

2.2 Women in Innovation – Win event

The project acknowledged that gender stereotypes also exist in the business sector and that more women in STEM is needed. To tackle these issues within the context of *T5.2 Engaging with the innovation ecosystems*, each GEP implementing partner had to organise an event (Win event). In particular, the WIN event had a two-fold aim: on one side it highlighted and valued women's led innovations presenting startups, spin offs and examples of gender sensitive product development/design; on the other hand, it worked as a means of raising awareness and attracting more girls to STEM research.

The following chapter presents the main results for each one of these events as they have been organised by each CALIPER RPO and RFO.

3 Reports of the events

This chapter presents the reports of the engagement activities per RPO/RFO. There are nine subsections, one per partner, containing the respective subsections with more details about each of the events organised by the CALIPER partners.

3.1 Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing – University of Zagreb (UZG – FER)

3.1.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The second awareness raising session was organized at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering on **May 17, 2022**. This second workshop was organized to present to, and discuss with, the Gender Equality Working Group of UZG-FER the progress of implementation of the Gender Equality Plan in the academic year 2021/2022.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker
12:30 – 12:35	Introduction	<i>Anamari Nakić</i>
12:35 – 12:55	Institutional governance	
12:55 – 13:15	Human resources	
13:15 – 13:35	Institutional communication	
13:35 – 14:20	Break	
14:20 – 14:40	Teaching & research	
14:40 – 15:00	Student services	
15:00 – 15:20	Activities in the next period	
15:20 – 15:30	Conclusions and closing	

Participants

In total, 6 participants attended the session (3 F, 3M). All participants were internal staff of UZG-FER, with 4 four them belonging to high management.

Table 1. Second awareness session at UZG-FER – Participants list

N.	Female/male	Position
1.	M	Head of Department of Electronic Systems and Information Processing / Research Group Lead
2.	F	Head of Committee for doctoral studies / Research group lead
3.	F	CALIPER project team member
4.	M	Vice dean / Research group lead
5.	F	CALIPER project principal researcher
6.	M	Ex dean / Research group lead

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The second awareness raising session was organized in the same fashion as the first one. All members of the Gender equality working group were invited. The leader of CALIPER project team presented the implemented activities of the institutional Gender equality plan. Actions were presented per thematic areas: institutional governance, human resources, institutional communication, teaching, research and student services. For each action, the circumstances of implementation were described: details of the action, timeframe, goals and conducted activities. Presentation of each implemented action was followed by discussion with all participants.

Minutes per thematic area

Human resources

One action was implemented: 3.2 Reporting on the status of gender equality. Within this action, the following activities were accomplished: organization of the system for collecting relevant data on the state of gender equality, creation of tools for the collection of relevant data, analysis of the data, and preparation of a report on the state of gender equality at UZG-FER for the period 2020 – 2022. The participants gave positive comments on the content of the report. After the review by the working group, the report should be also reviewed by the top management and made available to employees. Participants support the proposal that a report should be made biannually, that is, every two years.

Institutional governance

One action was implemented: 3.3 Pilot programme for empowerment of female researchers. The following activities were conducted: the design of a one-year pilot empowerment program for young female researchers; identification, and engagement of mentors (female role models who occupy leading positions in higher education and science and economy); and organization of workshops with mentors on the topic of leadership. The following online workshops were organized:

1. Prof. Brigita Miloš from the Department of Cultural Studies at the Faculty of Philosophy in Rijeka held an online workshop *STEM and Gender: Concepts and Contexts*, November 2021.
2. Prof. dr. sc. Nina Begičević Ređep, Dean of the Faculty of Organization and Informatics, University of Zagreb, held an online workshop *The position of women in management positions and their dominant leadership style*, December 2021.
3. Vedrana Miholić, CROZ sales manager, held an online workshop *Queen's gambit*, January 2022.
4. Rebeka Belavić from Q agency held an online workshop *Skills that are necessary for success, not written in the CV*, February 2022.

The number of participants was low, thus the WG supports the proposal not to repeat this action in the next academic year.

Institutional communication

One action was implemented in this area: 4.1 Establishment of a dedicated digital communication channel. The website is established (<https://www.fer.unizg.hr/ravnopravnost>) and is regularly updated with news about institutional activities in the area of gender equality. It will be used for the promotion of female researchers and conduction of communication campaigns for the Women in Science Day, Girls in ICT day, etc. Participants suggest making the website more visible and to add a link on the main page of the faculty website. The CALIPER team will contact the Centre for information support to see if this is possible.

Teaching and research

One action was partially implemented in the area of teaching: 5.1 Integration of the gender dimension in teaching. It is planned that this action will continue in the next academic year. The following activities were conducted: a group of teachers met in several seminars and group meetings, and an informal intuitive tool (i.e., check list) on the integration of the gender dimension into the curriculum was created. This checklist will be used to implement gender dimension into the curricula of a few courses in the next academic year. The participants support the implementation of this action.

In the area of research, one promotional action was implemented: 5.4 Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology transfer. The main output of the action was a two-day event FER-WIN (Women in Innovation) in April 2022. Two main sessions took place as follows:

1. Panel discussion: Women in Innovation (dr. Petra Maždin, Gideon, dr. Ivana Nižetić Kosović, Ericsson Nikola Tesla, dr. Ivana Stupar, Ericsson Nikola Tesla, dr. Anamari Nakić, UZG-FER)
2. Book presentation: First female scientists at FER (moderator Branka Marijanović, speakers assoc. prof. Mihaela Vranić, prof. Jelka Petrak, prof. Maja Matijašević, prof. Emer. Branka Zovko-Cihlar)

The main goal of the panel discussion was to present women in innovation, researchers that obtained their PhD degree at FER and then transferred to the industry, more concretely to the R&D department. In the conversation, they described their experiences from the doctoral study, lifelong motivation for research work and ongoing cooperation with researchers from FER. Almost 50 participants came to FER-WIN, both representing internal and external stakeholders. Some of the participants of the 2nd awareness session also took part in the event. Participants expressed support for this type of promotional activities and proposed to advertise them more and continue with the organisation in the future.

Student services

One action was implemented in the area of student services: 6.2 Attracting new female students. In this context, the following activities took place: identification and engagement of female role models from higher education and science and industry to promote women in STEM, organization of programming workshops for students. More than 150 elementary school students participated in the workshops, which were led by 20 female alumni of UZG-FER. WG members support this activity and proposes to continue it in the next year.

Other

It was proposed to introduce free female hygiene products in WCs. This proposal will be submitted to the management of the faculty.

Plan for the implementation of GEP for the next academic year 2022 / 2023 was presented to working group.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered. The meeting was very constructive and successful.

Conclusion

The conducted session accomplished the goal of awareness raising for members of the Gender equality working group of UZG-FER. WG members propose to make implemented actions permanent, where possible.

Supporting material

The presentation used for the second awareness raising session is available for download at the following link: <https://twk.pm/atuaritsl7>

3.1.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The third awareness raising session was organized at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering of University of Zagreb **on April 27, 2023, for Girls' in ICT Day**. The third workshop was organized to present to, and discuss with, the employees and the external stakeholders of UZG-FER the progress of implementation of the Gender Equality Plan in the period 2021 - 2023.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
11:00 – 11:15	Introduction	<i>Stjepan Bogdan</i>
11:15 – 12:00	Presentation of activities	<i>Anamari Nakić</i>
12:00 – 12:20	Institutional governance	
12:20– 12:40	Human resources	
12:40 – 13:30	Break	
13:35 – 14:20	Institutional communication	
14:20 – 14:40	Teaching & research	
14:40 – 15:00	Student services	
15:00 – 15:10	Conclusions and closing	

Participants

In total, 26 persons participated (19 F, 7M). The external stakeholders that took part were 4 from academia, 3 from industry, and 2 from government sectors. The number of participants belonging to high management was 9 (7 academia, 2 industry).

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The third awareness raising session was organized in a different fashion than the first two. While the initial ones were focused on the members of the Gender Equality working group, the participants of the third session were all employees who participated in the implementation of GEP activities, as well as external stakeholders from the CALIPER project. During the session, implemented activities of the institutional Gender Equality Plan were presented per thematic area: human resources, institutional communication, institutional governance, teaching, research, and student services. For each action, the circumstances of implementation were described: details of the action and conducted activities. The presentation of each thematic area was followed by discussion with all participants.

Minutes per thematic area

Vice-dean for research and innovation presented the faculty strategy and dedication in the area of gender equality. A member of the CALIPER project presented the implementation of GEP in the period 2021 – 2023 and led the discussion.

In the area of *human resources*, the results of two implemented actions were presented: *Reporting on the status of gender equality* and *Attracting and retaining female researchers*. Within the action *Reporting on the status of gender equality*, the following activities were accomplished: organization of the system for collecting relevant data on the state of gender equality, creation of tools for the collection of relevant data, analysis of the data and preparation of a report on the state of gender equality at UZG-FER for the period 2020 – 2022. The participants gave positive comments on the content of the report. Within the action

Attracting and retaining female researchers an exit survey for employees was designed and the data collection is ongoing. The collected data will enable better understanding of why individuals choose to leave academia and science and consequently give information by which the institution could adapt working conditions and offer opportunities to attract and retain female researchers.

In the area of *institutional governance*, one action was implemented: *Pilot programme for empowerment of female researchers*. A one-year pilot empowerment program for young female researchers was designed, and female role models who occupy leading positions in higher education and science and economy held 4 workshops on the topic of leadership. The following online workshops were organized:

1. *STEM and Gender: Concepts and Contexts*, prof. Brigita Miloš, University of Rijeka.
2. *The position of women in management positions and their dominant leadership style*, prof. dr. sc. Nina Begičević Ređep, Dean of the Faculty of Organization and Informatics, University of Zagreb.
3. *Queen's gambit*, Vedrana Miholić, CROZ sales manager.
4. *Skills that are necessary for success, not written in the CV*, Rebeka Belavić, Q agency.

The feedback of participants is supportive of organising workshops on enhancing leadership skills in young researchers. Collaborative actions with external stakeholders are supported.

In recent years, representation of women in faculty management improved. Usually one of 4 Vice-deans is a woman, which had been judged as a positive step forward.

A new Committee for insurance of equal opportunities is being set up as a permanent body of the Faculty Council, with the responsibility of design and implementation of a GEP.

In this area of *institutional communication*, the action *Establishment of a dedicated digital communication channel* is presented. The website is up and running. It is regularly updated with news and serves to promote female researchers and gender mainstreaming in research. Positive feedback has been received.

In the area of *teaching*, within the scope of the action *Integration of the gender dimension in teaching*, a checklist gender sensitive teaching for professors was created. The participants support the implementation of this action.

In the area of *research*, the action *Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology transfer* was implemented. A two-day event WIN was organised in April 2022. Participants expressed support for these types of promotional activities and proposed to advertise them more, and continue with organisation in the future. External stakeholders are interested in participation. A publication about the first female researchers who worked at the Faculty until 1970 was published and promoted.

In the area of *student services*, the action *Attracting new female students* was implemented. For Girls' in ICT Day, programming workshops for high school students were organised. The Faculty and IEEE Women in Engineering are producing a podcast ŽensCast featuring women in STEM. A dedicated website for future students was created with all the content.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered. The meeting was very constructive and successful.

Conclusion

The conducted session accomplished the goal of awareness raising for participants, both employees and external stakeholders.

Supporting material

The presentation used for the second awareness raising session is available for download in the following link: <https://twk.pm/fhoj9e7uk8>

Figure 1. Third awareness raising session at UZG - FER

3.2 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG)

3.2.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The organisation of the second awareness raising session **was split in two parts**. The first part took place on **July 7, 2022**, and the second on **July 26, 2022**.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
14:00 – 14:05	Opening and welcome speech	<i>Rusudan Jobava</i>
14:05 – 14:40	Presentation of CALIPER project	<i>Rusudan Jobava, Tamar Chkhaidze</i>
	Review of GEP activities, main results and achievements	<i>Rusudan Jobava, Tamar Chkhaidze</i>

14:40-14:55	Discussion on upcoming adjustments, potential new activities and prolongation of already implemented activities to 2 nd iteration	<i>All participants</i>
14:55-15:00	Conclusion remarks	<i>Rusudan Jobava</i>

Participants

The first part of the event was attended by 6 participants (5F, 1M); while the second part by 15 participants (10F, 5M). Internal stakeholders, representatives of the governmental sector, took part in both sessions. The participants were representatives of low and middle management.

Minutes

Due to concurrent COVID-19 restrictions, it was decided to organise the activities in an online format instead of face-to-face. The sessions started with a welcome speech and included presentations and discussion parts. The presentations mainly covered information about the CALIPER project, GEP activities per each area, key priority areas on which GEP is focused, and the results and achievements of the implemented efforts and activities foreseen for the future. Besides that, the speakers stressed the importance/need for the prolongation of some activities' implementation in the future and the significance of the development of new activities.

The session started at 14:00 and lasted 1 hour in each part. In total, the session was attended by overall 21 participants. The audience included internal stakeholders. Stakeholders and speakers for the session were identified 1-2 weeks in advance. During the session, there were no particular resistances identified. Instead, all implemented and discussed activities and GEP measures received positive feedback.

In comparison to the first awareness raising session, the number of participants was increased to 21 and more attention during the session was paid to the already implemented GEP activities.

The session covered its main goals, such as raising awareness about the CALIPER project and GEP activities. GEP's actions were supported by internal stakeholders, and they expressed their interest in further meetings and support for future implementation processes.

Supporting material

Figure 2. Second awareness raising session at SRNSFG: Snapshots from online sessions

3.2.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The third awareness raising session was implemented virtually on **March 13, 2023**.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
16:00 – 16:05	Opening and welcome speech	<i>Rusudan Jobava</i>
16:05 – 16:40	Presentation of the CALIPER project and review of GEP activities, main results and achievements of the 1 st iteration, review of activities for the 2 nd iteration	<i>Rusudan Jobava, Tamar Chkhaidze</i>
16:40-16:55	Discussion on upcoming adjustments, potential new activities and prolongation of already implemented activities to 2 nd iteration	<i>All participants</i>
16:55-17:00	Conclusion remarks	<i>Rusudan Jobava</i>

Participants

The session gathered 10 participants (9F, 1M). Internal stakeholders and representatives of the governmental sector took part in the session. The participants were representatives of low and middle management.

Minutes

The SRNSFG partners opted to also organise this final session in an online format=. The session started with a welcome speech and included presentations and discussion on the scope of the meeting and the overall vision of the project. The presentations mainly covered information about the CALIPER project, GEP activities per each area, key priority areas on which GEP is focused, the results and achievements of implemented activities and future upcoming activities.

Stakeholders and speakers for the session were identified 1-2 weeks in advance.. During the session there were no particular resistances identified. Instead, all implemented and discussed activities and GEP measures received positive feedback. In comparison to the previous awareness raising session, more attention during the session was paid to the upcoming and implemented GEP activities from the research funding area.

The session covered its main goals including raising awareness about the CALIPER project and GEP activities. GEP's actions were supported by internal stakeholders, and they expressed their interest in further meetings and support for future implementation process.

Supporting material

Figure 3. Third awareness raising session at SRNSFG: Snapshots from online session

3.2.3 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

Having organised a WIN event on 2022 (as documented at D5.6 – Engagement activities reporting v2), the SRNSFG held the 2023 edition of the event on **Saturday 17 July**. The event was organized in collaboration with R&I Hubs aiming to highlight and value women’s’ led innovations, successful career stories and examples of different initiatives helping of raising awareness and attracting more girls to STEM research. The 2023 edition also included the award ceremony for the 2023 Rustaveli National Science Foundation prize competition "Women in Science".

Agenda

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

First session: Welcoming speeches

Second Session: Round Table

Third Session: Women in Innovation

Final Session: Award Ceremony of "Women in Science" 2023 prize

Participants

The event was attended by 46 people consisting of SRNSFG top management, Ministry representatives and stakeholders from prominent Higher Education Institutions that are part of the national CALIPER R&I Hub.

Minutes

Description of the process and structure of the event:

Research innovators from various Georgian universities and research centers, as well as representatives of the public sector, donors and non-governmental organizations were invited to the conference.

The purpose of the conference was to present the activities of female scientists and innovators representing the STEM direction, share experience, raise motivation and promote female scientists. Promotion of active participation in research, raising public awareness of gender equality, promotion of participation of women and girls in scientific research.

Erekle Astakhishvili, Director General of the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia, Mariam Lashkhi, a member of the Standing Parliamentary Council on Gender Equality and the Culture and Education Committee of the Parliament, Professor Zaza Maruashvili, Deputy Head of the Science Development Department of the Ministry of Education and Science, Rector of Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University welcomed the audience in their opening speeches.

Jaba Samushia, Deputy Representative of UN Women Tamar Sabedashvili, Deputy Rector of Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Professor Nino Okribelashvili, Associate Professor of Ilia State University Tamar Tskhadadze, were the keynote speakers of the second session of presentations.

Rusudan Jobava, Head of the International Relations and Fundraising Service of Rustaveli National Science Foundation, presented a presentation about the CALIPER project. The key points of her presentation highlighted valuable results of CALIPER for SRNSFG, listed as follows:

- Gender Equality Plan (GEP);
- Award competition - "Women in Science" - for special achievements in the STEM direction;
- Section on the website "Women in Science", where information about successful Georgian women scientists is placed;
- The mechanism for checking gender equality in scientific projects;
- Guide for members of the expert panel;

In order to share the experience of women scientists and innovators working in the STEM direction, presentations were made by: Professor of Technical University of Georgia, candidate of technical sciences, winner of the Foundation's 2022 applied research grant competition, Lana Shatakishvili, Ph.D., representative of the Agrarian University, winner of the 2022 applied research grant competition, Eka Metreveli, the founder and executive director of the "IT Academy Step Georgia" branch, Maka Makhatadze, and the doctor of geological sciences, professor of San Diego State University, Elina Bakradze.

- Brochures, guides on raising awareness;

At the end of the event, the winner of the 2023 Rustaveli National Science Foundation prize competition "Women in Science" was awarded to the Doctor of Biology, Tamar Khardziani.

Supporting material

Figure 4. WIN Event 2023 at SRNSFG

Figure 5. WIN Event 2023 at SRNSFG: Award ceremony

3.3 Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava – Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU BA)

3.3.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The second round of STU BA's awareness sessions was organised in conjunction with the institution's WIN event and the internal session with GEP WG members **on Tuesday, May 17, 2022**. The session was held in a one day back-to-back format that was dedicated to bringing into the spotlight the University's efforts to introduce gender balance as well as the gender dimension into its research. The detailed reporting of the first two events can be found in the previous version of the current deliverable, that is *D5.3 – Engagement activities reporting v1*.

The day was split into 3 blocks, and the second awareness session was the final block of the day. It was held virtually via the Google Meet platform and lasted for an hour.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
14:00 – 14:10	Presentation of HR Award of Excellence	<i>prof. Ing. Milan Edl, PhD.</i>

14:10 – 14:20	University of Žilina in the context of internationalization and institutional changes	<i>prof. Ing. Jozef Ristvej, PhD.</i>
14:20 – 14:30	Instrument of Institutional Change – Gender Equality Plan at Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information	<i>Mgr. Zuzana Staňáková, PhD</i>
14:30 – 14:40	Keynote speech	<i>prof. Ing. Robert Štefko, PhD.</i>
14:40 – 14:50	Open discussion	<i>All participants</i>
14:50 – 15:00	Conclusions & ending of the day	<i>All participants</i>

Participants

Being co-located with the previously reported WG workshop and the WIN event, the online awareness session was attended by a total of 97 people, comprised of 61 women and 36 men, as this has been documented in D5.3.

Minutes

The awareness session constituted Block C, the third and final part of a vivid whole-day event on the 17th of May, 2022. The session was initiated with a presentation from Prof. Ing. Milan Edl, PhD. who is a Dean at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering ZCU Plzeň, presenting the “HR Award of Excellence”. Following that, prof. Ing. Jozef Ristvej, PhD. Vice-Rector for International Relations and Marketing at the University of Zilina presented the topic "University of Žilina in the context of internationalization and institutional changes". The next presenter was Mgr. Zuzana Stanakova, PhD representing the Science Support Section, who gave a presentation titled "Instrument of Institutional Change – Gender Equality Plan at Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information". Finally, Prof. Ing. Robert Štefko, PhD. who is the Dean at Faculty of Management, Economics and Trade (University of Presov) contributed to the session with a keynote speech, an overview and outlook to the future of the addressed topics regarding gender equality.

At the very end of the event, some guests provided quality feedback, highlighted the most interesting findings, and commented on the course of the event in general. The responses were very positive and pleasing.

Supporting material

The figure consists of 21 numbered presentation slides from STU BA, organized into a grid. The slides cover the following topics:

- Slide 10:** Interné hodnotenie (Internal Evaluation) - VÝZVY (CHALLENGES). Focuses on the gender equality of the student body and the number of students in the 1st and 2nd stages of the BA program.
- Slide 11:** Interné hodnotenie (Internal Evaluation) - VÝZVY (CHALLENGES). Focuses on the transfer of research results to the MTF STU BA and the participation of MTF STU BA researchers in research projects.
- Slide 12:** Interné hodnotenie (Internal Evaluation) - VÝZVY (CHALLENGES). Focuses on intersectionality and sexual harassment, highlighting the need for a gender equality policy and the importance of a safe environment for research.
- Slide 13:** Interné hodnotenie (Internal Evaluation) - VÝZVY (CHALLENGES). Focuses on intersectionality and sexual harassment, providing statistics on the number of respondents and the prevalence of various forms of harassment.
- Slide 14:** Externé hodnotenie (External Evaluation) - PRÁVNY A POLITICKÝ RÁMEC (LEGAL AND POLITICAL FRAMEWORK). Discusses the legal and political framework for gender equality in the Slovak Republic.
- Slide 15:** Externé hodnotenie (External Evaluation) - INOVÁČNY EKOSYSTÉM (INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM). Discusses the innovation ecosystem and the role of gender equality in research and development.
- Slide 16:** Externé hodnotenie (External Evaluation) - ANALÝZA SIETOVANIA - SPOLUPRÁCE (NETWORK ANALYSIS - COOPERATION). Analyzes the network of stakeholders and the role of STU BA in the research ecosystem.
- Slide 17:** Externé hodnotenie (External Evaluation) - PLÁNOVANÉ AKTIVITY NA ĎALŠIE OBDOBIE (PLANNED ACTIVITIES FOR THE NEXT PERIOD). Lists planned activities for the next period, including the application of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) and the promotion of gender equality in research and development.
- Slide 18:** Plán rodovej rovnosti STU BA (Gender Equality Plan STU BA) - PLÁNOVANÉ AKTIVITY NA ĎALŠIE OBDOBIE (PLANNED ACTIVITIES FOR THE NEXT PERIOD). Focuses on the implementation of the GEP, including the role of the Gender Equality Institute and the promotion of gender equality in research and development.
- Slide 19:** Plán rodovej rovnosti STU BA (Gender Equality Plan STU BA) - PLÁNOVANÉ AKTIVITY NA ĎALŠIE OBDOBIE (PLANNED ACTIVITIES FOR THE NEXT PERIOD). Focuses on the implementation of the GEP, including the role of the Gender Equality Institute and the promotion of gender equality in research and development.
- Slide 20:** Plán rodovej rovnosti STU BA (Gender Equality Plan STU BA) - PLÁNOVANÉ AKTIVITY NA ĎALŠIE OBDOBIE (PLANNED ACTIVITIES FOR THE NEXT PERIOD). Focuses on the implementation of the GEP, including the role of the Gender Equality Institute and the promotion of gender equality in research and development.
- Slide 21:** Plán rodovej rovnosti STU BA (Gender Equality Plan STU BA) - PLÁNOVANÉ AKTIVITY NA ĎALŠIE OBDOBIE (PLANNED ACTIVITIES FOR THE NEXT PERIOD). Focuses on the implementation of the GEP, including the role of the Gender Equality Institute and the promotion of gender equality in research and development.
- Slide 22:** ĎAKUJEME (THANKS). A closing slide expressing gratitude for the participation in the awareness-raising session.

Figure 6. Second awareness raising session at STU BA: Presentation slides

Čas (CET)	Aktivita	Inštitúcia
10:00	Otvorenie, privítanie hostí	STUBA
	Interný workshop	
	prof. Mgr. Dagmar Cagaňová, PhD. Zodpovedná riešiteľka projektu H2020 CALIPER, STU BA „Predstavenie Plánu rodovej rovnosti (GEP) v rámci projektu CALIPER“	STUBA
	Ing. Veronika Mešková H2020 CHANGE projektová manažérka pre UNIZA, koordinátorka úlohy výskumu a vývoja	UNIZA
	Mgr. Alena Rusnáková, PhD. Oddelenie spoločenských vied, TUKE	TUKE
	prof. PhDr. Alexandra Bitušiková, CSc. Riaditeľka Univerzitného centra pre medzinárodné projekty, UMB Banská Bystrica	UMB
	prof. Ing. Miloš Poliak, PhD. Dekan FPEDAS UNIZA „Zamestnávanie žien v cestnej nákladnej doprave na pozícii vodič/vodička“	FPEDAS UNIZA
	Otvorená diskusia – O&O	All
11:30 – 12:00	Prestávka	
12:00	Mladí ľudia a inovácie - Win event	
	Mgr. Alexandra Blažeková Staple bread & necessities, manažérka	MITF-STU Staple bread & necessities
	Ing. Lenka Hlinková Ženský algoritmus, n. o., výkonná riaditeľka	Ženský algoritmus, n. o.
	Ing. Ivana Nováková Konateľka spoločnosti Aponi, s. r. o., start-up centrum TUKE	Aponi, s. r. o.
	Prezentácie start-up projektov študentiek a študentov pod vedením doc. Ing. Michala Baloga, CSc. (vedúci KPII, FVT TUKE)	
	Bc. Anastasia Hnidets a Andrii Hryn	FVT
	Bc. Diana Lazarenko	FVT

Program stretnutia [17/05/2022]

Strana 2 z 2

Čas (CET)	Aktivita	Inštitúcia
	Bc. Yulia Sytar	FVT
	Otvorená diskusia – O&O	All
13:50 – 14:00	Coffee break	
14:00	Online awareness session	
	prof. Ing. Milan Edl, PhD. Dekan, Strojnícka fakulta ZCU Plzeň „HR award of excellence“	ZCU Plzeň
	prof. Ing. Jozef Rlstvej, PhD. Prorektor pre medzinárodné vzťahy a marketing, ŽU „Žilinská univerzita v kontexte internacionalizácie a inštitucionálnych zmien“	UNIZA
	Mgr. Zuzana Staňáková, PhD Sekcia podpory vedy „Nástroj inštitucionálnej zmeny - GEP CVTI SR“	CVTI
	prof. Ing. Robert Štefko, PhD. Dekan FMEaO PU	PU
	Otvorená diskusia – O&O	All
15:00	Záver podujatia	STUBA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 7. Second awareness raising session at STU BA: Whole-day program

3.3.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The STU BA project team organised the third awareness raising session on January 26, 2023. The event was held online and consisted of updates and commentary on the implementation of GEP at the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava. The goal was to expand the communication platform and evaluate the effectiveness of the GEP implementation.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
13:00 – 13:30	Presentation of GEP Actions	Miriám Šefčíková

Participants

The online session was attended by internal employees from various positions such as researchers, professors, managers, teachers and the deanery. In total, 33 participants were engaged in the session; female participants were 21 and male ones were 12.

Minutes

The session approached the topic of gender equality and its importance for the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava. Based on the discussions, it has been made evident that the establishment of GEP actions is essential at two levels. The first concerns all the internal staff of the Family in interpersonal relations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

at the workplace, in teaching, in communication, etc. The second level consists in respecting the conclusions of the analysis of the European Commission and the implemented European gender equality policy, which promotes the standardisation of GEPs' application in research organisations that apply for European framework programmes.

Supporting material

Invitation post at the university's portal: https://www.mtf.stuba.sk/sk/diani-na-mtf/aktuality/pozvanka-na-seminar-rodova-rovnost-na-mtf-stu.html?page_id=16550

Figure 8. Third awareness raising session at STU BA

3.4 Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB)

3.4.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The aim of the second awareness session was to promote reflection and raise awareness about the implementation of structural gender equality measures at the ULB. The session took place **on January 20, 2022**, as a hybrid event (both onsite and online attendance). The session was intended to present the scope of possible structural action, in terms of the legal framework of affirmative action to all internal stakeholders and promoting active engagement and awareness about affirmative actions.

In particular, the objectives of the awareness session were:

- To present the legal framework of affirmative action in terms of structural measure at the ULB to internal stakeholders.
- To present and raise awareness about existing affirmative action for structural measure in other national university and international university.
- To promote the reflection about internal resistances in affirmative actions' implementation at the ULB.

- To launch reflection about strategic guidelines to promote active engagement on finding new solutions and application of affirmative actions at the ULB.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
10:20 - 10:30	Opening and welcome speech	<i>Isabelle Rorive, teacher & president of Equality Law Clinic Laurent Licata, researcher & teacher in social psychology + CALIPER team member</i>
10:30 - 11:00	Presentation of the feasibility study result about affirmative action	<i>Titouan Berhaut-Steel, phd student and member of Equality Law Clinic Student working for Equality Law Clinic</i>
11:00 - 11:20	Q&R	<i>All participants Equality Law Clinic member</i>
11:20 - 12:00	Roundtable - Possible affirmative action at ULB - Resistances/ obstacles - Strategy	<i>Internal stakeholders</i>

Participants

In total, 12 participants attended the session. The composition of the participants was diverse comprising members from the academic council, academic staff of the university and students.

Table 2. Second awareness session at ULB – Participants list

Type of participants	Number & gender ratio	Name
Internal stakeholders	5 participants - 3 W - 2 M 2 top level management : VR + academic council	Lidjia Stefanoska Patricia Melotte Michel Verstreten Dimitri Leemans Sandra Arndt
Academia & universities members	5 participants - 2 W - 3 M	Claudia Thomas Laurent Licata Isabelle Rorive Titouan Berhaut-Streel Robin Medard Inghilterra
PhD students & Students	2 participants - 1 W - 1 M	Joseph Mumbanza Ngeke Hortense Van Look

Minutes

Topic: Presentation of the feasibility study result about affirmative action

Main issue addressed: Legal framework

- European policy on affirmative action
- Legal framework of affirmative action in Belgium law

Key outcomes and remarks:

The EU does not oblige the member states to apply this positive action policy, but the European policy represents an exception to the right of equal citizenship. For its application the following conditions must be met:

- If one gender is under-represented
- If the measure is not permanent
- Flexibility of the action

In the French community, in Belgium, there is a decree submitted but not yet approved to put affirmative action with this condition:

- Data for under-representation of a gender
- Goal has to be oriented on the reduction of the gender inequality
- Not permanent
- Not unnecessarily restrict the rights of others

Main issue addressed: Affirmative action in other Universities; 6 measures listed

- Pre- Recruitment
- Recruitment
- Post-recruitment

Key outcomes and remarks:

- Pre- Recruitment
 - Measure 1: allocation of training places (Badeck ruling)
 - Measure 2: Invite as many women as men to job interviews
- Recruitment
 - Measure 3: Give priority to women with the same qualifications as men
 - Measure 4: Redefine merit in selection decisions
 - Measure 5: Promotion to combat the "leaky pipeline" phenomenon
 - Measure 6: Participation on Boards and Commissions

Main issue addressed: Possible future action for ULB

Key outcomes and remarks:

Adoption of a positive action plan through the Royal Decree. No challenge possible

The CALIPER project can be inspired by the Royal Decree 2019 too.

The responsibility of Belgium in the international order can be engaged if it fails in its obligation to apply a law.

Topic: Roundtable

Main issue addressed: Possible affirmative actions at ULB

Key outcomes and remarks:

Some affirmative action already exist and have been voted by internal stakeholders, such as:

- Cascade measure
- Gender balance in advisory board

Proposition was to continue working on this measure and farer (ex: Measure 5: Promotion to combat the "leaky pipeline" phenomenon)

Main issue addressed: Resistances and obstacles

Key outcomes and remarks: The measures of the affirmative action do not have a legal framework in Belgium. Implementing other affirmative action can be a risk for ULB.

Main issue addressed: Strategy

Key outcomes and remarks:

Internal stakeholders agreed on the strategy below such as a response of the obstacles:

- Re-work on the decree for affirmative action in the French community to put pressure on politics to pass it in the legal framework.
- In parallel, initiate a consultative process to write new affirmative action for recruitment and structural change.

In conclusion, internal stakeholders gained awareness about the legal framework in Belgium but also the possibility of implementing new affirmative action. Obstacles were discussed and the roundtable elaborated on viable solutions.

Supporting material

Figure 9. Second awareness raising session at ULB: Invitation flyer

The presentation used for the second awareness raising session is available for download in the following links:

- [Equality Law Clinic](#)
- [CALIPER - Roundtable](#)

The session has been recorded and it is available to watch on demand in the following link: [\[Recording\]](#)

3.4.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The session was organized on **07 February 2023**, at ULB with the members of the steering committee to discuss about progress in the implementation of GEP actions, to reflect on strategies and ways forward for GE actions, the long-term durability of these as well as approaches to mitigate against potential obstacles and to receive advice and support to secure key resources for the project. Importance was given to provide an overview of the state of play of the project and to focus in on key actions that needed support and strategic advice as well as to update the members and raise awareness on achievements that have been made in the project.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
10:20 - 10:30	Progress updates in the GEP: Overview & State of play regarding the GEP activities	Indra Weber

10:30 - 11:00	Actions for decision making & discussion	<i>All participants</i>
11:00 - 11:20	Progress updates and way forward on other actions & Discussion	<i>All participants</i>
11:20 - 12:00	Roundtable & Conclusions	<i>All participants</i>

Participants

In this session 9 persons took part on a ratio of 4 males to 5 females. The stakeholders came from academia with 2 of them belonging to top management positions.

Minutes

The session started with a presentation by the CALIPER team of the GEP actions currently being implemented (3rd iteration) according to the designed timeframe. The members received a state of play on the project and updates on each action which were followed by discussion per action. Actions were divided into those that needed key decisions to be taken as well as strategic support and actions where achievements and important updates could be shared.

Below is a selection of key actions and discussions.

M12 : Consultation for the integration of sex/gender+ diversity perspective into STEM curriculum competency framework

Goal: Advocate for the possibility to integrate a dedicated sentence on the gender dimension in the competency framework i.e. **'Profil enseignement'**

Status/way forward

- Deans FS/EPB, confirmed they are ready to support the action
- CAP developed and presented a formulation based on 4 dimensions of competences that future professional would require → After deliberation the CoPil will review and agree on the formulation to be proposed (See slide 6)

The gender + commissions should be involved.

We can not only propose a mention – but must provide resources for academics to be able to practically integrate the gender dimension into their teaching plans.

The entire process and adoption of the special mention may take time beyond the duration of CALIPER – as the support of many actors need to be secured

M13: Consultation for support activities/resources to integrate the gender dimension into the STEM teaching qualification program

Name has been changed [Originally "Consultation for a new ULB science and technology qualification program to teach at secondary schools"]

>> Due to reform in the entire qualification program ongoing but with extensive timeline – 2024 onwards – action has been revised.

Refined Goal: raise awareness of/advocate for the gender dimension in qualification of secondary school teachers.

Way forward:

Cooperation and proposal for action to be set up with WG on 'Pacte pour un Enseignement d'Excellence : mathématiques, sciences, géographie – formation manuelle, technique, technologique et numérique'.
[FWB] -Thomas Barrier & Team.

- Note: Reform cannot be directly influenced but through the WG for teaching excellence a practical and immediate impact on secondary teaching will be achieved through provision of resources and a training.

M4: Action-oriented study 'Extension of post-doctoral contracts for the duration of childcare leaves

X Action is being started

GOAL:

- Understand state of play - map measures on extensions- across '**External**' **post-doc funding** sources.
- **Find the gaps where no extension is given** – who is not covered & propose ways to support post-docs not covered.

Way forward/decisions

- The Research Department – should agree to conduct the mapping exercise.

M17: Review/update communication of current STEM websites

Goal : Review primary webpages of STEM faculties for inclusive language and imagery [EPB&FS]

Status/way forward

- ✓ CALIPER will recruit student Jobbers [2 – 1 for each faculty]
- ✓ # of primary & secondary websites in each faculty identified [37 pages FS | 41 pages EPB]
- ✓ 12h / jobbist as a start
 - 1.5h training with specialist in inclusive comms) [jobbists & comms managers]
 - Jobbists perform revisions in 2-3 weeks following the training.
 - → Comms managers of each faculty supervise and specify way of working/how they want revisions to be implemented practically.
- Anticipated completion – hopefully by beginning May.

NOTE: revisions should seek to avoid point median - •e – rule when possible. Approach should be to turn communications inclusive in a general way e.g., mentioning both genders in the text.

M19: Training discrimination & harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities

Goal: sensitize teaching staff at EPB & FS to any gender/sex biases/stereotypes in underrepresented domains – i.e. STEM

Status/way forward

- ✓ Training: "Lutter contre les stéréotypes et favoriser la mixité dans les STIM" – executed by JUMP
- ✓ 2 sessions
- The deans agree to support the measure and help to push outreach to secure participants.

M10: Exhibition 'Sex/gender+ in STEM research'

Goal: launch poster exhibit to raise awareness of the gender dimension in reserch and innovation

- ✓ **EPB & FS (+WomenInTech) for INTERNATIONAL DAY OF WOMEN & GIRLS IN STEM** – 11 Feb

Spotlight: Woman scientists across both faculties – Research excellence

- 90+ registrations (mainly ULB students and some externals)
- 13 speakers | 7 moderators
- **13-18 Research posters – also showing gender dimension in research**
+ **Dedicated posters on the gender dimension.** + **WOW women role models** and plenty of awareness raising.

Way forward: support for outreach to secure participants agreed. Also, a budget is provided for the event.

M6. Gender indicators in different STEM disciplines

Way forward

- Process agreed to now be centralised. Redefinition of Gender Report: to now include faculty specific indicators – efforts are now streamlined.
- STEP will conduct the indicators:
 - Set of basic indicators for EPB & FS will be provided at: Faculty & Disciplinary level.
 - 3 levels: Students | Staff | PATGS
 - Publication strategy TBC – 1 Public vs. 1 Internal (sensitive data)

M16: Training - inclusive communication – website administrators

- ✓ Training successfully held with positive feedback
- Just waiting on survey questions to launch evaluation
- ✓ 19 Participants across both faculties
- ✓ Session 2 in May – share learning outcomes and impacts achieved

M11: Guide on gender-sensitive teaching

- ✓ READY Anticipated publication mid Feb 2023

Dissemination/way forward

- 1) Prof de aggregation training future teachers: CAPAS
 - 2) CALIPER network: CoPil | Website STEM faculties
 - 3) Newsletters: <https://actus.ulb.be/fr/actus/enseignement>
- Members agree to support diffusion.

ROLE MODEL VIDEO

Goal: Create engaging video that features a diversity of women across career stages and inspires a next generation of female scientists.

Status

- ✓ all 4 Role models confirmed
 - ✓ Filming begins soon
- Final video expected beginning April.

Way forward: commitment to support access to locations and more women to be featured in the video has been agreed.

CALIPER FINAL CONFERENCE

Goal: Wrap up the project and share results, create future possibilities – bring together community of practitioners

- ✓ **23 NOVEMBER 9-16H – FULL DAY 9-16h**

.... More info coming soon.

Conclusions

Overall, there is good commitment and general support for the GEP and the values it represents. No outward resistance could be anticipated but there are some obstacles to be overcome to successfully realise all actions and secure their sustainable impact. The committee agreed to keep working together with the CALIPER team to progress the GEP, to provide valuable strategic input along the way and for different members to play a role in realizing different actions.

Supporting material

State of play – all actions by JULY 23

7 COMPLETED	7 PARTIALLY
M2: Feasibility of affirmative actions for academic recruitment	M1: Toolkit to attract more female candidates to STEM positions [OK, by May]
M5: Gender+ Commissions	M6: Gender Indicators [1 st set in March]
M7: Proposal for a gender-balanced participation in Advisory Boards	M10: Exhibition 'Sex/gender+ in STEM research' [11 Feb]
M15: Joint ULB-g4g event (day of STEM exploration)	M11: Guide Gender sensitive teaching [publication in Feb]
M18: Dedicated webpage for the gender+ measures of STEM faculties (EPB & SF)	M12: Consultation- Integration of gender perspective into STEM curricular competency framework [proposals today]
M16: training inclusive communication for STEM webpages [Session 2: May]	M14: Gender technical support for STEM outreach [planned by end May]
M8: Target for PhD Juries – [Faculties to send documentation]	M19: Training discrimination & harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities (to be fixed)
4 – In progress	
M9: guideline gender dimension in research (in progress) [Delayed]	M13: Consultation - new STEM & tech qualification prgm to teach at secondary schools [changed! TBC]
M17: Review/update comms of STEM websites – student jobbers – from mid feb/March – May?	M3: Action-oriented study 'Correction standard for career breaks due to childcare leaves' [Feb-June]

4 dimensions de la compétence des futures professionnel.les

L'étudiant.e soit être capable de :

Disciplinaire :

- mettre à jour ses connaissances scientifiques disciplinaires et transdisciplinaires (incluant les genderstudies)
- développer un rapport critique et épistémique aux savoirs sous une perspective de genre

Méthodologique :

- utiliser le genre-sexe comme catégorie d'analyse et comme outil méthodologique dans ses travaux de recherche
- transposer les savoirs touchant au genre à ses pratiques et tâches professionnelles

Sociale :

- gérer les situations professionnelles de collaboration et de leadership de façon non discriminante en intégrant la perspective de genre
- avoir une communication inclusive

Réflexive:

- identifier les biais de genre potentiels dans son travail de recherche et dans ses pratiques professionnelles
- réguler ses actions en intégrant les données probantes des la littérature

Figure 10. Third awareness raising session at ULB

3.5 School of electrical and computing engineering – National Technical University of Athens (ECE-NTUA)

3.5.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The CALIPER team organised a back-to-back awareness raising session and focus group discussion on the overall implementation process. The meeting was realised online, through the MS Teams application on **Monday 27th of June 2022**. The aim was to inform the participants about the progress of the project, focusing on the implementation of the GEP actions. The second scope of this meeting was (through discussion with the participants) the following:

- The evaluation of the 1st year of implementation of the School's Gender Equality Plan,
- Detection of possible schedule deviations,
- Proposals – additions – changes to the Gender Equality Plan (for the 2nd year of implementation)

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
11:00 – 11:10	Opening and welcome speech	Dr Emmanouil Ntanos
11:10 – 11:30	Presentation of GEP Actions	Dr Emmanouil Ntanos
11:30 – 12:00	Focus Group discussion	All participants

Participants

Invitations have been sent to 21 contacts. All members of the WG were invited, as well as selected administrative, research, and academic staff. The response rate was lower than expected (5 participants). The issue was discussed within the session, and it was concluded that since it took place during the exam period, the academic as well as the administrative staff would be quite busy.

As such, the CALIPER team will adapt its approach to improve participation in future sessions.

The total number of participants were 5 (M/F Ratio: 3/2), while also 3 members of the CALIPER Team were present (M/F Ratio: 1/2). Their allocation is presented in the following table:

Table 3. Second awareness session at ECE-NTUA – Participants list

N.	Female/male	Position
1.	M	Academic staff, Member of the Deanery
2.	M	Teaching & Research Laboratory staff
3.	F	Teaching & Research Laboratory staff
4.	F	Teaching & Research Laboratory staff
5.	M	Administrative staff
6.	M	CALIPER project team member
7.	F	CALIPER project team member
8.	F	CALIPER project team member

Minutes

Scope and Methodology

The second online awareness session was followed by the focus group discussion. Main goal was to present the implemented activities of the Gender equality plan, at all the members of the WG. Additionally, aim was to receive feedback through the focus group discussion to identify possible barriers, share ideas and solutions for the 2nd year of GEP's implementation.

Minutes

Dr Ntanos initiated the session by welcoming the participants and sharing the scope of the meeting. Subsequently, he presented the organizational structure, the participants in the implementation of the GEP, along with their roles.

Afterwards, Dr Ntanos gave an overview of all the actions of the GEP that have started or have been completed in the 1st iteration (2022-2023). For each action, the presentation included a description of the main achievements and results so far, as well as the main barriers and delays inhibiting its implementation.

Once the awareness part of the session was completed, the following issues were raised in order to encourage the audience to participate in the discussion, as per the evaluation methodology:

- Suggestions for improving organizational issues, human resources adequacy
- Suggestions for avoiding barriers/resistance, alternative strategies
- Assessment of project goals and visibility, suggestions for improvement
- Evaluation of structural actions (planning, timeframes, proposals for improvement)
- Discussion for the annual anonymous questionnaire (survey's length, launching etc)

One of the participants claimed that, regarding the organizational issues, the team should focus on the problems that may have arisen during the implementation phase in order to find solutions, since people outside the team do not have a clear view of the whole process. She, and others as well, also added and

repeatedly insisted, that to address the low engagement of students in events/workshops/seminars, the team should invite a student as a speaker, organize a “welcome presentation” at the beginning of the academic year for the new students or even participate in a students’ assembly to present the project. Among the ideas on how to attract more students was to reach students’ organizations and students’ representatives, both for speakers and audience, since students are the main beneficiaries of this effort. This will also enhance the project’s visibility.

Regarding the engagement of the top and middle management (deanery, heads of the departments and laboratories), the participants suggested that the team should organize follow-up presentations in order to keep them informed and motivated.

Moreover, a comment for a specific GEP action was made by the professor of the group. He mentioned that it is quite difficult to convince a professor to add in his lecture some extra slides regarding gender equality since he/she has already a specific plan for each lecture. On top of that gender equality cannot be applied easily on the most of the School’s courses due to their technical nature.

The group was also asked to comment on the progress of the project’s targets. Dr Ntanos highlighted that the structural actions seem to be more challenging than the team had predicted. A participant added that the low visibility can be a barrier on the implementation of these actions, since the awareness levels are not sufficient.

The group agreed that a possible reason why the engagement of the teaching and administrative staff is low, is the lack of the respective official regulations and of central (NTUA level) formal guidelines.

Regarding the Gender Equality Office and the relevant barriers relating to its establishment (human resources, responsibilities), the participants suggested to run it in pilot mode with people from the CALIPER team, since the School’s official procedures take time and will hinder the action.

Another question raised from the teaching staff member was if there is a budget, in the project’s framework, dedicated for the GEP actions of each partner. Since the answer is no (apart from the corresponding man months for the team regarding the management/organization/implementation of GEP actions) and since the School has not committed to any of these actions, their implementation becomes more difficult and time consuming.

Regarding the Questionnaire, there was a suggestion to print it and share it in the exams, but the group concluded that this is not an efficient way to reach more participants.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered.

Conclusion

The awareness session was not particularly successful in terms of participation, and the project team will explore different approaches to improve the outreach of future events. To this end, the participants agreed to avoid meetings during exam periods due to the workload of the target audiences. The focus group discussion, on the other hand, was fruitful, and the team gained important feedback to proceed with the actions’ implementation and redefine some approaches.

Supporting material

Figure 11. Second awareness session at ECE - NTUA

Questions for the implementation of the Focus Group (in Greek)

Focus Group / Interviews

Structure: Σύντομη αναφορά στην οργάνωση του έργου, των δράσεων και στο ανθρώπινο δυναμικό.

- 1) Πώς πιστεύετε ότι μπορεί να βελτιωθούν τα οργανωτικά ζητήματα του έργου/οι διαδικασίες λήψης αποφάσεων; Θεωρείτε ότι το υφιστάμενο ανθρώπινο δυναμικό επαρκεί; Θα μπορούσε να γίνει αποδοτικότερα η κατανομή των αρμοδιοτήτων;

Process: Σύντομη αναφορά στην εφαρμογή των δράσεων. Εμπόδια (εξωτερικά), αντιστάσεις (εσωτερικές) αποκλίσεις από τον αρχικό προγραμματισμό, καθυστερήσεις, εξωτερικοί συμμετέχοντες.

- 2) Θεωρείτε αναμενόμενες τις καθυστερήσεις και τα εμπόδια; Τι θα μπορούσε να είχε γίνει διαφορετικά προς αποφυγή των εμποδίων κλπ.; Πώς θα μπορούσαν να ξεπεραστούν τα θέματα αυτά στο μέλλον; Μπορείτε να προτείνετε κατευθύνσεις για μια αποδοτικότερη στρατηγική; Υπάρχει κάποιος άλλος από το εξωτερικό περιβάλλον που θα μπορούσε να συμμετάσχει για τη βέλτιστη υλοποίηση των δράσεων;

Objectives: Σύντομη αναφορά στο τι έχει γίνει έως τώρα

- 3) Θεωρείτε ότι έχει επιτευχθεί ο σκοπός του έργου μέχρι σήμερα; Τι θα μπορούσε να είχε γίνει διαφορετικά/καλύτερα; Πού θα μπορούσε να δοθεί περισσότερη έμφαση; Η ορατότητα του έργου θεωρείτε ότι είναι σε επιθυμητό επίπεδο;

Future Structural Activities: Σύντομη αναφορά στις δράσεις αυτές.

- 4) Ποια είναι η άποψή σας για τις δράσεις αυτές; Θεωρείτε ότι θα έχουν αντίκτυπο; Είναι ρεαλιστικός ο σχεδιασμός τους και τα χρονικά περιθώρια που έχουν τεθεί; Τι θα μπορούσε να σχεδιαστεί διαφορετικά;

3.5.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The CALIPER team organised the third awareness raising session **on the 10th of April 2023**, through the online platform MS TEAMS. The aim was to inform the participants about the progress of the project (2nd iteration), focusing on the implementation of the GEP forthcoming actions. The following key points were discussed:

- 1st iteration: Concluded actions
- 2nd iteration: Concluded actions
- 2nd iteration: Actions under development, recommendations, possible synergies
- Sustainability potential after the end of the project

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
13.30 – 13.35	Opening and welcome speech	Dr Manolis Ntanos
13.35 – 13.55	Presentation of GEP Actions: Concluded actions and future goals	Dr Manolis Ntanos & Dr Maria Flouri
13.55 – 14.30	Discussion	All participants

Participants

Members of the WG were invited as well as researchers and members of the administrative staff, in order to further disseminate the actions and collect feedback. Apart from the 3 members of the CALIPER team (M/F Ratio: ½) that were present, the total number of participants were 11 (M/F Ratio: 4/7). Their allocation is presented in the following table:

Table 4. Third awareness session at ECE-NTUA – Participants list

N.	Female/male	Position
1.	M	Academic Staff, Member of the Deanery
2.	F	Administrative Staff
3.	F	Administrative Staff
4.	F	Researcher
5.	F	Administrative Staff
6.	F	Researcher – Permanent staff
7.	M	Researcher
8	M	Researcher
9	F	Researcher
10	F	Researcher – Permanent staff
11	M	Administrative Staff
12	M	Member of the CALIPER Team
13	F	Member of the CALIPER Team
14	F	Member of the CALIPER Team

Minutes

Scope and Methodology

Main goal of the 3rd awareness session was to present the implemented GEP activities during the 1st and 2nd iteration, as well as to present the forthcoming planned activities, in order to receive feedback from the participants. Moreover, at the end of the session a brief discussion took place on the sustainability of the actions after the end of the project. This provided the CALIPER Team with input such as ideas and potential cooperation synergies.

Minutes

Dr Ntanos and Dr Flouri welcomed the participants, while sharing the session's main scope and targets. Dr Ntanos initiated the session by presenting the following points:

- 1st iteration: Concluded actions
 - Role models and dissemination actions
 - Application of the Guide for the use of non-sexist language in the public documents

- Integration of gender equality in the School's courses and lectures
- Framework for the researchers working conditions
- WiN Event
- Data Collection on gender and intersectionality

Consequently, Dr Flouri continued the presentation, through the following points:

- 2nd iteration: Completed actions
 - Establishment of the GE Office
 - Internal targets for the desired percentage of female representation and the integration of gender into research
 - Adoption of procedures and mechanism to handle incidents of bias, sexist behaviour, sexual harassment and gender violence
 - Seminar on gender issues for students
 - Open Days
 - Integration of gender equality in the School's courses and lectures
- 2nd iteration: Actions under implementation
 - Alumni network
 - Women in STEM Network
 - Data Collection on gender and intersectionality
- Sustainability potential

After the presentation the discussion continued on the procedures and mechanism to handle incidents of bias, sexist behaviour, sexual harassment, and gender violence. The relevant Guide has been disseminated via email and through the ECE NTUA official website, while all participants were also informed regarding the GE Office announcement section on the School's website. (<https://www.ece.ntua.gr/gr/announcements>).

The second issue that was raised related to the difficulty of attracting and engaging students in the various GE events. One participant suggested the solution of using the students email lists that are used by the Dean and/or the Rector Office. Using these lists requires permission by the Dean and/or the Rector, however, the Gender Equality Committee could assist towards this end. At this point the CALIPER team mentioned the presentation of gender issues to students, during the presentation of the School's specialization streams. A leaflet was handed to all attending students, with a QR code for anyone interested in subscribing to the GE activities.

The attendants discussed the 2nd Annual GE Questionnaire, to be launched by June 2023. The idea is to cooperate with the GE Committee, in order to elaborate a common/adjusted Questionnaire, which would be disseminated to all members of NTUA, (i.e. all NTUA schools and services) . More data will be collected this way, while also working to increase awareness on GE issues.

As regards the action "Application of the Guide for the use of non-sexist language in the public documents", although completed, the participants agreed that it would have best results if its training seminar were to be repeated. That way the seminar would be addressed to all administrative personnel of the School, and not only to the personnel of the Secretariat. Moreover, the CALIPER Team proposed the elaboration and dissemination of a relevant brochure, that would include basic guidelines on the implementation of the Guide.

Moving on, the discussion focused on how gender integration on more courses is possible. One participant (tenured researcher) was interested in doing so in the lectures she gives in the field of Biomedicine and Microsystems.

The participants were informed that the next students' seminar on gender issues will be in October, during the welcoming of the 1st semester students. They also highlighted the importance of balanced representation when presenting the School to secondary education Schools, to Open Days etc.

Finally, one participant proposed the idea of a "Girls Day", an event only for young girls and women from secondary education who are interested in STEM. That way the School could attract more female students.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered. The meeting was rather constructive.

Conclusion

The discussion was successful, and the CALIPER team gained important feedback, ideas and knowledge for its future actions, as well as for their sustainability.

Supporting material

Figure 12. Third awareness session at ECE – NTUA

3.6 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB)

3.6.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The main purpose of the session was to provide a broad summary of the status of the actions of the Gender Equality Plan, and the actions that are being developed. The session was carried out **on Thursday April 28, 2022**, in the framework of the Equality and Diversity Committee periodic meetings which summons a good attendance and representation of different members of the Institute. As other awareness sessions planned and developed at the IRB, the main idea is not only to inform, but also to gather feedback, comment on good practices and generate involvement on current or future plans to be developed in the framework of CALIPER'S GEP or other actions on the topic of equality and diversity.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
11:30 – 11:45	Presentation and EDC involvement	Neus Prats
11:45-12:45	GEP Update	Marcelo Mora & CALIPER WG members
12.45 – 13:00	QA +Comments	ALL

Participants

In total 13 participants attended the session with a 23% male to 77% female ratio. All the participants came from the Academia sector, with 4 of them representing high/top management positions.

Minutes

Scope and Methodology

The session was held onsite having the participation of various stakeholders representing various areas and departments of the Institute. The main difference from previous sessions was that this session was held completely “offline” which provided a much better interaction among the participants.

Prior to the meeting a list of the topics was sent to the confirmed participants, to engage better interaction with the topics (GEP actions) but also it provided an open question in case any of the participants wanted to suggest any topic to be discussed during the meeting.

Minutes

GEP Update: *The actions that were in “progress” were presented and discussed with the participants. An important emphasis was done on the timing and expected result for each of the actions, and how they should be reported through the monitoring and evaluation template. The following actions were explained:*

- Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach.
- Conduct a salary audit regarding equal pay: Special explanation of how it was going to be developed by a third party/outsourced company
- Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol: update on possible new calls for the remainder of the year and how to put the protocol in action.
- Prepare an internal regulation to govern the Equality and Diversity Committee
- Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan.
- Promote institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics (videos, institutional equality day, printed materials, among others): **International Women’s Day Video:** *The video was shown and discussed among the participants. Highlighting the importance and involvement of members of the scientific to me involved in this type of activities. The video can be watch through this link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qdLtw5cNj48&ab_channel=IRBBarcelona*
- Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.
- Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment.: Evaluate new and better communication channels in case the protocol is activated.
- Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality.: Prisma EVENT to be done at the IRB Barcelona in June 2022
- Win Event: Changes of date, and possible structure for the event.

Other topics discussed during the meeting:

- Work-life balance measures: Yoga classes
- “Dones I Ciència en Barcelona”: discussion of the involvement of the local government in equality and diversity activities.
- Mentoring Programmes: “Formació en lideratge para dones científiques”
- New ways of evaluating CVS and jobs applications: DORA method.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered.

Conclusion

The main remarks of the session were the following:

- *For active working groups in GEP actions, the importance of keeping material and updated working log was specially emphasis.*
- *Measures of WLB should be put back in order with a new structure after the pandemic measures are lifted*
- *The involvement of men in developing the actions of the GEP has a lot of importance within the community, and more participation among members of the scientific community will be encouraged.*
- *An effort will be made to include more activities like the International Women’s day video since it created an important amount of engagement and interest.*

Supporting material

Figure 13: Second awareness session at IRB

Human Resources

The actions targeting human resources come about from the results of an internal assessment and the legal framework. These actions are focused on three key areas: Recruitment, Equal Pay, and Work-Life Balance.

Through the following actions, IRB Barcelona will channel increased efforts into promoting knowledge of existing department policies and guidelines, promoting an establishing gender-sensitive approach to human resources practices. With regard to work-life balance, the focus is to promote work-life balance practices in the Institute and create awareness of the importance of a pro-conciliation leadership management model.

HUMAN RESOURCES			
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach.	Broaden knowledge of recruitment measures, policies and protocols on the part of the IRB Barcelona community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRB Barcelona community Stakeholders involved in the recruitment process (Hiring Managers and Panel members involved in the process) 	October – November 2021
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Conduct a salary audit regarding equal pay	Ensure equal treatment and nondiscrimination among men and women with regard to pay	All those on the IRB Barcelona payroll.	October 2021- December 2022
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Plan and develop training actions to raise awareness of the importance of work-life balance and implement a pro-conciliation leadership management model.	Make work-life balance effective, enhancing an institutional culture in which the promotion and support of conciliation are highly valued	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Middle and Top Management Heads of Scientific and Administrative Departments 	January 2022- Continuous

Institutional Governance

The actions for Institutional Governance were designed to promote and enhance measures to support equal opportunities for men and women.

Actions were planned following two key areas: Promoting Career Progression and supporting the figure of the Equality and Diversity Committee.

Career Progression actions are focus in offering mentoring programs, providing leadership and decision-making skills. In addition, existing protocols related to Group Leader positions will be consolidated and disseminated in order to promote the participation of women in this role.

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE			
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Develop mentoring programmes to promote career progression.	Provide a guidance method for career progression reflecting commitment to the career development of women .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Postdoctoral community Junior Group Leaders 	October 2021- Continuous
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol.	Increase awareness of the protocol, its advantages,	Internal and external stakeholders involved in Group Leader selection processes	October 2021- Continuous
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Prepare an internal regulation to govern the Equality and Diversity Committee	Provide a document regulating the functioning of the Equality and Diversity Committee and the roles of its members.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRB Barcelona community Equality and Diversity Committee 	January 2022- July 2022

Institutional Communication

The topic of gender equality is increasingly present in the Communications department at the IRB Barcelona. Important efforts are being made to ensure that IRB Barcelona's internal and external communications reflect diversity and gender equality.

The idea of the new communication actions implemented in the Gender Equality Plan is to enhance these efforts and provide policies and guidelines to support the implementation of gender sensitive approach in the Institute internal and external communication plan.

INSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATION			
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan.	Raise institutional awareness of efforts to be made in matters pertaining to equality and diversity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRB Barcelona community • External stakeholders 	October 2021- Continuous
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Creation and promotion of manual/guidelines on inclusive language (English, Spanish, and Catalan)	Include gender sensitivity in internal/external communications.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundraising, Communication & Marketing Department • Human Resources Department • Equality and Diversity Committee • IRB Barcelona community 	July 2022- December 2022

Institutional Communication

Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Develop a checklist/guidelines for posting and checking material on the Institute's social media channels.	Provide a guide to ensure the gender sensitivity of external communication on social media platforms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundraising, Communication & Marketing Department • Human Resources Department • Academic Unit • Equality and Diversity Committee • IRB Barcelona community 	July 2022- December 2022
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Organise and participate in advanced training on inclusive language.	Integrate an inclusive (gender, diversity, intersectional) approach into oral and written communications and apply the recommendations for diverse and inclusive communication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundraising, Communication & Marketing Department • Human Resources Department • Equality and Diversity Committee 	January 2022- March 2022
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Promote institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics (videos, institutional equality day, printed materials, among others).	Give greater visibility to the efforts made by IRB Barcelona with respect to equality and diversity topics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRB Barcelona community • External stakeholders 	October 2021- Continuous

Young Scientist

The IRB Barcelona has adapted the “Student Services” category initially set by the framework to the Caliper Project and modified to fit the structure of the Institute, renaming this category as “Young Scientist”. This change has been made because the IRB Barcelona is not a dedicated teaching center, but a scientific Institute.

Even though, the institute does not have enrolled students it does serve as workplace for young scientist to start their scientific career. To support the evolution of scientific careers with a gender perspective, the actions for “young scientist” pretend to provide tools through training actions, to provide a context of the commitment of the institute with equality and diversity. These training actions will provide information of the existing measures the institute has in regards to equality and diversity such as the existence of an Equality and Diversity Committee, mentoring programs, measures in integrating gender dimensions into research and innovation, among other.

YOUNG SCIENTISTS			
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.	Give all newcomers a general overview of efforts made at IRB Barcelona e in matters pertaining to quality and diversity.	All newcomers	October 2021- Continuous
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Integrate gender perspective training in transversal PhD programme.	Include a mandatory course to inform about existing initiatives addressing equality and diversity.	PhD Students	September 2023-June 2024

IN BIOMEDICINE

Sexual and Gender Harassment

The IRB Barcelona has a strong commitment in creating an inclusive and safe workplace. To support this, the IRB Barcelona created in 2012 the protocol for dealing with, preventing and eradicating workplace harassment.

Through the internal assessment analysis, the results indicated that not all the IRB Barcelona community is aware of such protocol and the existence mechanism of how to address harassment situations.

Actions to offset these situations have been included in the Gender Equality Plan. The actions are focused on two main areas: training, and reviewing and disseminating existing protocols and documentation to provide and support a safe environment in the IRB Barcelona.

SEXUAL AND GENDER HARASSMENT			
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Develop internal training on Sexual & Gender Harassment	Increase awareness and capacity to prevent and recognise sexual and gender harassment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health and Safety Unit • Equality and Diversity Committee • Human Resources Department 	March 2022- Continuous
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment.	Prevent and eradicate behaviours related to sexual and gender harassment.	IRB Barcelona community	October 2021- January 2022

Intersectionality

The IRB Barcelona, through the actions and involvement of the Equality and Diversity Committee has taken a broader approach from a binary perspective to equality towards a more intersectional approach, taking into account other aspects that converge and influence gender equality, such as social class, ethnicity, the existence of disability, and sexual or gender orientation, among others.

To reinforce this approach and to improve important aspects that were highlighted in the internal assessment, the actions for the intersectionality topic will be based in training actions and awareness campaigns. The objectives of these actions will be to provide a better knowledge of intersectionality topics to members of the Equality Commission and Equality and diversity Committee and to provide a better overall perspective of intersectionality topics to the IRB Barcelona Community.

INTERSECTIONALITY			
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality.	Construct a critical perspective on intersectional topics, providing the grounds to rethink everyday practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equality and Diversity Committee IRB Barcelona Community 	January 2022-Continuous
Action	Main Goal	Target Audience	Time Frame
Organise an advance training session on gender and diversity topics for members of the Equality Commission.	Provide an advance perspective on the concept of equality and diversity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equality Commission CALIPER Working Group Equality and Diversity Committee 	January 2022-July 2023

Figure 14. Second awareness session at IRB – Snapshots from GEP actions updates

3.6.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

This part contains information of two meetings that were combined to represent the “3rd awareness session” for the IRB Barcelona.

The first meeting was held with members of various sectors of the institute, as was done for the 2 previous awareness sessions.

The second meeting that complements this report was the institutional Faculty meeting, in which a portion of the event was dedicated to update the participants on the development of GEP actions and the involvement of Faculty members.

Agenda

Part 1 – Internal meeting:

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
11:00 – 11:30	CALIPER Project Updates	Marcelo Mora
11:30 – 11:45	Development of actions	Marcelo Mora

	Feedback of the Inclusive Language Course/ Leadership Course	
11:45 – 13:00	List of Potential Courses planned for 2023	<i>Discussion within all members</i>
	Participation of external Working Groups	
13:30 – 13:10	Conclusions and open discussion	<i>Discussion within all members</i>

Part 2 – Faculty Meeting:

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
13:00 – 13:30	CALIPER Project Update & development of actions	<i>Neus Prats (Chair of EDC)</i>
13:30-14:30 (sessions carried out in parallel)	How to improve diversity at IRB Barcelona?	<i>Alejo Rodriguez (Group Leader)</i>
13:30-14:30 (sessions carried out in parallel)	Equality and Diversity training for managers	<i>Antoni Riera(Group Leader)</i>
13:30-14:30 (sessions carried out in parallel)	Gender balance in decision-making positions	<i>Direna Alonso (Group Leader)</i>
13:30-14:30 (sessions carried out in parallel)	Wellbeing at work	<i>Maria Isabel Labrid (Head of HR)</i>
14:30-15:00	Discussion and Conclusion	<i>Neus Prats (Chair of EDC)</i>

Participants

In regard to the first internal meeting, 10 people took part in, of whom 8 were female and 2 were male, while all of them represented the Academia sector (3 members of high/top management).

Regarding the second meeting held in Faculty level, 40 members of the Faculty participated, all them representing the academic sector. The participants' ratio was 14 females to 26 males. The participants were all members of high management, either Group leaders or Head of Departments.

Minutes - Internal Meeting

Scope and Methodology

The meeting was held onsite, and it was encouraged to be as participative as possible, gathering feedback and opinions from participants.

Minutes of the internal meeting

Caliper Project updates:

6 actions are done and reported, 6 more are done and their report is pending. In June there is an in-person meeting to present the results, and some of the actions need to be finished for then. Some of the actions need to be reprogrammed for next year, probably. Marcelo will be in contact with the people involved in

organizing this. There is space and budget for more trainings and actions in order to take as much out of the project as possible before it is finished.

List of Potential Courses planned for 2023 (Organized by the EDC and CALIPER project):

1. Inclusive language in English and Spanish/Catalan for all the IRB. We think that we could have an open session followed by a hands-on session at the end. Different registrations will have to be done and hands-on will be restricted. The Catalan/Spanish will be coordinated with the release of the Inclusive language guide by AQuAS. Martina and Sònia will take care of the organization (EDC).
2. Time management: there is an offer from the BIST but we still think that there is space for this training (EDC).
3. Gender bias and other biases to raise awareness in the broad public (EDC).
4. Harassment training (EDC).
5. Advanced training on diversity topics for the equality commission (CALIPER)
6. Integrating gender dimension (CALIPER)
7. Work-life balance and pro-conciliation measures for leaders and manager (CALIPER)

Use of institutional Blog for promoting GEP actions: role model videos as an example

Participation with external groups such as Athena project:

Interviews to members of the Caliper project to explain the benefits of having a GEP, expertise gained during the generation of the GEP

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered. The meeting was rather constructive.

Minutes - Faculty Meeting

Scope and methodology

This meeting is organized periodically at the IRB to discuss several topics among Group Leaders and Heads of Departments at the IRB. Having all of these members reunited, provided the ideal platform to explain and discuss Equality and Diversity topics and how to generate involvement within Faculty members. This was the first time Equality and Diversity topics were discussed in this manner at a Faculty meeting, so having this opportunity the idea was to divide the provided time into two different sections. The first section was to provide an update of the CALIPER Project and an overall summary of finished and ongoing GEP actions. The second part of the session was focused on generating involvement, and to accomplish this, participants were divided into 4 groups to discuss different topics.

Minutes of the Faculty Meeting

- ***Main outcomes/remarks:***

Group 1. Topic: - How to improve diversity at IRB Barcelona?

- *Develop a feedback process to understand the situation of foreigners*
- *Enhancing visibility/recognition*
- *Housing Advice support*
- *Peer mentoring for minorities*

- maximize international recruitment

Group 2. Topic: Equality and Diversity training for managers

- Prevention of harassment seminar/course
- Gender inclusion into research
- Wellbeing at work
- Time Management

Group 3. Topic: Gender balance in decision-making positions

- Inform about specific calls for female scientists
- Value other activities like participation in committees
- Institutional responsibilities: Give more visibility
- Specific Career Progression and Leadership training and mentoring programs

Group 4. Topic: Wellbeing at the IRB

- Psychological service
- A standard training of Time Management for all the community
- Involve the leaders in a Wellbeing at work training

Resistances

It was commonly commented that more time could have been useful to be allocated to the meeting because of its great context and important topics addressed, but the consensus was that this was a great opportunity.

Supporting material

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion at IRB

- What E,D&I means?
- *What are we doing at IRB Barcelona?*
- *How managers can create and sustain a Diverse and Inclusive workplace?*

What Equality, Diversity and Inclusion means?

DI-VER-SI-TY

All the ways in which people differ.

EQ-UI-TY

Fair treatment, access, opportunity, and advancement for all people. One's identity cannot predict the outcome.

IN-CLU-SION

A variety of people have power, a voice, and decision-making authority.

Definitions sourced from City of Portland Office of Equity and Human Rights, The Independent Sector, and UC Berkeley.

Means:

Fairness: ensuring that we all have the best possible opportunities to succeed in life and career, whatever our origin or identity.
Specific things need to be done for different groups to ensure that everyone has the opportunity to get the same result.

What are we doing at IRB-Barcelona?

- Equality and Diversity Committee
- H2020 Project- Caliper (2020-2023)
- Equality Commission
- Equality Plan (2021-2024)
 - Human Resources (7)
 - Institutional Governance (5)
 - Institutional Communication (5)
 - Research (2)
 - Young Scientists (2)
 - Addressing Gender and Sexual Harassment (2)
 - Transfer to market (2)

New Guidelines and Policies
Trainings, Workshops, Round tables
Networks and Synergies (Hypatia, Prisma, Amit, CDC-CIC, etc)

Gender balance in science?

Tiura de gènere dels centres de recerca de salut de Catalunya

4

How managers can create and sustain diverse and inclusive workplace ?

Be aware that it is not just the responsibility of Human Resources and actively consider and promote equality in everything we do:

create a workplace in which people understand and respect differences in gender, race, religion, cultural values and thinking styles

understand prejudice, discrimination, harassment and the consequences of engaging in discriminatory practices

Effectively ED&I management systems results in increased productivity and innovation, less discouraging and career failure, over and above contributing of high performance research systems

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INSTITUTE
FOR RESEARCH
IN BIOMEDICINE

How managers can create and sustain diverse and inclusive workplace ?

Is not only responsibility from Human Resources. We have to actively consider and promote equality in everything we do:

- creating a workplace where individuals understand and respect the differences in gender, race, religion cultural values and thinking styles
- understand bias, discrimination, harassment and the consequences for participating in discriminatory practices

The effectiveness of E&D&I management systems translates into increased productivity and innovation, less discouragement and career failure, over and above the contribution of high-performing research systems.

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So, let's divide in working Groups 20 min

Group 1 *Alejo Rodriguez*

How to improve diversity at IRB Barcelona?

Group 2 *Antoni Riera*

Equality and Diversity training for managers

Group 3 *Maribel Labrid*

Wellbeing at work

Group 4 *Direna Alonso*

Gender balance in decision-making positions

10 min- Results presented by the rapporteur of the Group
5 min- Summary and final conclusions

7

Project Development

COMPLETED ACTIONS		ONGOING ACTIONS		PENDING ACTIONS	
Human Resources	3	Human Resources	3	Human Resources	2
Institutional Governance	3	Institutional Governance	1	Institutional Governance	0
Institutional Communication	3	Institutional Communication	1	Institutional Communication	1
Research	0	Research	2	Research	0
Transfer to Market	1	Transfer to Market	0	Transfer to Market	1
Student Services/ Young Scientist	1	Student Services/ Young Scientist	0	Student Services/ Young Scientist	1
Sexual and Gender Harassment	1	Sexual and Gender Harassment	1	Sexual and Gender Harassment	0
TOTAL	12	TOTAL	8	TOTAL	5

Implementation of actions

Figure 15. Third awareness session and Faculty event at IRB – Snapshots of the issues presented

3.6.3 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

The IRB's WIN event took place on **Tuesday, June 14, 2022**. The event began at 15:00 and it was divided in three sessions, including a round table, a networking part and a dynamic workshop. The event was planned taking into consideration different points of view and it was designed fostering the collaboration among different stakeholders and the exchange of ideas. The main organisation and planning were done by the CALIPER WG in close collaboration with the Innovation Department of the IRB Barcelona.

Agenda

Introduction of the session

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Round Table: Women in Innovation

Coffee Break/ Networking space

Workshop: Design thinking with a gender perspective

- Defining the concept of Design thinking
- Dynamic group sessions
- Presenting results

Q&A

Conclusion

Participants

The event was attended by a multitude of stakeholders from the IRB Institution, the R&I Hub established within the project and additional third parties of the IRB's network. In total, 50 participants attended the WIN event, the majority of whom came from IRB (37), while 8 of them were affiliated with organisations of the IRB R&I Hub. 5 of them with other external parties. In regards the representation, there were 5 male and 44 female participants, along with a person opted to not disclose their gender.

Minutes

Description of the process and structure of the event:

The overall idea and concept for the WIN event was to highlight the role of women in innovation, analysing different perspectives and points of view from women in different stages, positions and roles in the entrepreneurial ecosystem and the factors that contribute to reaching their goals/objectives. The following perspectives were highlighted:

- **Junior entrepreneurs:** Young women entrepreneurs with a recently established startup/spin off.
- **Senior entrepreneurs:** Consolidated women entrepreneurs, with an established company that started as an entrepreneurial endeavour.
- **Innovation department:** Understanding and analysing the role of an innovation department and its role within the entrepreneurial endeavour.
- **Innovation regional overview:** Having the point of view of individuals outside the IRB with an overview of the general innovation and entrepreneurial scope from a regional perspective.

Based on the above approach, the event's first session consisted of a Round Table in order to have the participants interact and share their experiences and points of view through their perspective and personal experiences. The Round Table served as an instrument to understand the steps that women innovators take in order to achieve their entrepreneurial objectives, the support they get and the barriers they have to face.

In order to further expand the two main concepts of the WIN Event ("Innovation" and "gender equality"), a workshop was also organised on "design thinking in innovation with gender perspective" to complement and further progress the ideas elaborated during the Round Table.

The workshop was delivered by WeEQUAL, a consultancy company with expertise in supporting the corporate empowerment of women and diversity in the workplace. WeEQUAL is focused on helping grow companies that promote equal opportunities and diversity and inclusion.

The workshop included a brief introductory section introducing the concept of "Design Thinking" followed by a hands-on interactive section. It provided a general overview of what design thinking in innovation with a gender perspective is.

A coffee break was offered between the Round Table and the Workshop, where the attendees had the opportunity to network in an informal and more personal setting.

People in charge of WI event, and main contributors

Organisation Team:

CALIPER WG

- Maria Isabel Labrid, Head of the Human Resources Department- IRB Barcelona
- Neus Prats, Core Facility Manager and Chair of Equality Diversity Committee -IRB Barcelona
- Sonia Saborit, Section Head Pre-Award Grants - IRB Barcelona
- Martina Gasull, Lab Manager- IRB Barcelona
- Marcelo Mora, Project Manager- IRB Barcelona
- Maria Jesus Macias, Group Leader - IRB Barcelona

Directorate

- Margarida Corominas, Managing Director- IRB Barcelona

Innovation Team

- Cristina Horcajada, Head of Innovation Department- IRB Barcelona
- Tiago Oliveira Botelho, Senior Business Development Manager- IRB Barcelona

Communication Department

- Sara Martorell, Social Media & Alumni Relations Officer- IRB Barcelona

Round Table Participants:

- Sanja Zivanovic, CEO & Founder at SKIN MOLECULE
- Nuria Marti, Director of Innovation and Business Development- Biocat
- Cristina Horcajada, Head of the Innovation Department - IRB Barcelona
- Eva Vila-Massanas , Founder of WeEqual

Workshop Moderators:

- Eva Vila-Massanas- Consultant, expert in Design Thinking- WeEQUAL
- Gema Aguiló Consultant, expert in Design Thinking-WeEQUAL

Main remarks

The main idea was to highlight the experiences of women through the “innovation and entrepreneurial journey”, understanding the main barriers and challenges they face. The participants of the Round Table provided a broad overview of their experiences and personal challenges. As the topic developed, the second part of the Round Table gave the opportunity to the speakers to provide suggestions and areas of improvement to solve the challenges each of them presented. Finally, the participants shared their general overview of how they would motivate other women to pursue their innovation and entrepreneurial journey.

This structure of the round table served as a tool to provide a general overview from three different perspectives of the role of women in innovation, which perfectly matched with the objective of the WIN event.

The “design thinking workshop” was intended to provide a “tool” to analyse and plan new ideas, goals, or any objective participants may have in their professional careers. The session was oriented through a gender sensitive perspective, having an interactive session in which 4 different groups had the task to answer, with

the guidance of the experts the following question: *“How might we help our teams to innovate with a gender perspective?”*.

The dynamics of the workshop session gave the opportunity to have a collaborative interaction among the attendees in order to develop and understand the concept of “design thinking”.

Main outcomes

A series of conclusions were made in the event, having in consideration the interactions of the round table but also complimented by the dynamics of the workshop. The conclusions were documented as follows:

- Training is crucial.
- Mentoring Programmes are key in the development of women in innovation.
- Equality and diversity should be taken into consideration in the conformation of panels, speakers, boards, product testers, among others.
- Networking should be considered as a very important tool in the innovative and entrepreneurial journey. Women should improve their networking rate.
- In the innovation ecosystem, “empathy” should be highly valued and set into practice.
- Data of the development of women in innovation should be always present in order to educate and generate awareness.

Conclusions on the event

- The overall development of the event met the expectations of both the organizational team but also of the participants.
- The interactive sessions provided a great atmosphere for networking, but also to the learning of a new topic such as “design thinking”.
- The event set a good precedent for future interactive events and gave the organizational team a good experience of how to organize similar activities.
- There are still areas of improvement, such as how to better communicate this type of events and increase engagement within the community in order to raise awareness (especially in men).

Supporting material

Dissemination of the event:

To properly communicate the event and obtain engagement both internally and externally, the following communication channels were used:

Email invitation:

Following the institutional “message to all” structure the invitation of the event including all of the details and agenda was sent to the whole IRB Barcelona community. The invitation also included the following [registration link](#), which provided the details of the attendance of the session. This email format was also used as a reminder the week prior to the event. The invitation sent was the following:

Dear all,

We are pleased to invite you to the “Women in Innovation Event”. This gathering is one of the initiatives based on our new Gender Equality Plan, in which IRB Barcelona understands the importance of creating a vision where **equality, diversity, and inclusion** are valued by the entire community, avoiding bias and stereotypes.

The event aims to showcase women-led innovation by presenting start-ups and spin-offs and examples of gender-sensitive product development.

Information:

Date: Tuesday 14 June

Time: 15:00-17:30

Place: Parc Científic de Barcelona. Carrer de Baldori Reixac, 10 **Sala DOLORS ALEU**

Event Structure:

Round Table: Women in Innovation

Participants:

- Sanja Zivanovic, CEO & Founder of SKIN MOLECULE
- Nuria Marti, Director of Innovation and Business Development- Biocat
- Cristina Horcajada, Head of the Innovation Department - IRB Barcelona
- Eva Vila-Massanas, Co-Founder of WeEqual

Coffee Break

Interactive Workshop: “Design Thinking with a Gender Perspective”

If you would like to join us, please register at the following link: [IRB Women in Innovation Event](#).

The workshop will be limited to 50 people. Please indicate in the registration link if you wish to attend. The first 50 people to register will receive an email confirming the invitation to the workshop.

Best regards

IRB Barcelona Caliper Working Group

Figure 16. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – email invitation

IRB Barcelona - Women in Innovation
Event

[Iniciar sesión en Google para guardar lo que llevas hecho. Más información](#)

Name
Tu respuesta

Institute/Company/University
Tu respuesta

Email
Tu respuesta

Which part of the event are you attending

Round Table
 Workshop (Limited to 50 people)
 Both

Gender

Female
 Male
 Non Binary
 I dont wish to answer

Enviar Borrar formulario

Figure 17. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Registration form

In addition to the above, the IRB Barcelona has a weekly message that is sent to all of the community with a brief description of all of the events happening during the concurrent upcoming month. Hence, the WIN event was featured in the *'Plan your Week'* institutional communication. What is more, periodical mails were sent to the IRB community during the 3 weeks prior to the event.

The invitation in this mail is the following:

Tuesday 14 June

Other events

WIN event of CALIPER

Round Table: **Women in Innovation**
Interactive Workshop: **“Design Thinking with a Gender Perspective”**

Speakers:

Sanja Zivanovic, CEO & Founder at SKIN MOLECULE

Nuria Marti, Director of Innovation and Business Development- Biocat

Cristina Horcajada, Head of the Innovation Department - IRB Barcelona

15:00h - 17:30h

Monday 27 June

Other events

Tribute to Dr. Joan J. Guinovart, Emeritus Professor at IRB Barcelona

Registration

12:00h / Auditorium room: Antoni Caparrós (PCB)

Figure 18. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Weekly message

The WIN event was also promoted through the institutional social media, including a brief description of the event and the registration link. In addition, live updates were being posted during the activity in the IRB’s social media to broaden the visibility of the event. Examples of such social media posts are presented below:

Figure 19. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Social media posts

In order to support the diffusion of the WIN event messages, attendees of the event who represented IRB R&I Hub stakeholders also promoted the sessions through their communication channels. Examples include the following:

Figure 20. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Retweets from attendees

Figure 21. WIN event at IRB Barcelona

Figure 22. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Roundtable

Figure 23. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Hands on exercise

Figure 24. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Coffee Break and Networking

Figure 25. WIN event at IRB Barcelona – Workshop key question

Figure 26. WIN event at IRB Barcelona - Workshop hands on exercise

3.7 Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI)

3.7.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

This awareness-raising session was conducted on **24th October 2023** at UEFISCDI Head Quarters. The primary objective was to analyse and disseminate the preliminary results of a gender perspective analysis on the projects funded by UEFISCDI in recent years. This analysis forms a crucial part of our ongoing Gender Equality Plan (GEP) efforts.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
12:00 – 11:10	Opening and welcome speech	Alex Dinu
12:10 – 12:20	Overview of Gender Analysis in Funding - UEFISCDI	Alex Ionescu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

12:20 – 12:50	<i>Presentation of Key Findings from Analysis</i>	<i>Oana Ionescu</i>
12:50 – 13:10	<i>Strategies for Future Gender Equality Actions</i>	<i>All</i>
13:10 – 13:20	<i>Conclusions and Closing Remarks</i>	<i>All</i>

Participants

The event was attended by 8 participants in total. The female-to-male ratio was 5 to 3. One participant came from a high/top management position.

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The session began with an opening speech by Alex Dinu, setting the context for the meeting and emphasizing the importance of gender perspectives in research funding. This was followed by a detailed overview of the gender analysis methodology and its scope, highlighting any deviations from previous sessions.

Main outcomes and remarks

Key findings from the analysis were then presented, revealing insights such as gender leadership parity in national research institutes and public universities, distinct gender dynamics in teams, and the correlation between PhD holders and project leadership. Notably, the analysis uncovered gender-specific research niches and leadership pathways, as well as yearly fluctuations in project submissions.

The discussion segment allowed participants to delve into these findings, addressing potential resistances and challenges. Key outcomes from this discussion included the recognition of the need for more gender-specific initiatives and policies, especially in leadership roles, and the importance of maintaining high research quality standards irrespective of gender.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered

Conclusion

The session concluded with strategies for future actions to promote gender equality in research funding, emphasizing the role of UEFISCDI in leading these efforts.

Supporting material

In the vast spectrum of the academic and research landscape, national research institutes and public universities are pillars of innovation, knowledge dissemination, and discovery. Analyzing these entities from a gender perspective uncovers profound insights into their operational dynamics, leadership narratives, and broader strategic trends. By juxtaposing the gender trends within these two entities, we gain a holistic understanding of the gender landscape in national-level academia and research, while also identifying unique characteristics and patterns specific to each.

A. 10 Key Findings from an Overarching and Comparing Analysis:

1. **Gender Leadership Parity:** Both national research institutes (INCD) and public universities exhibit commendable gender balance in leadership roles, though slight male dominance can be discerned in both.
2. **Distinct Gender Dynamics in Teams:** INCD showcases more female representation within project teams, while public universities display a broader equilibrium.
3. **PhD and Gender Intersection:** In both institutions, a strong correlation exists between having a PhD and leading successful projects, irrespective of gender.
4. **Gender-specific Research Niches:** Within public universities, female-led projects tend to navigate more towards innovative and pioneering domains.
5. **Leadership Pathways:** The gender distribution suggests potential leadership pathways that could be further nurtured within both entities, especially for females.
6. **Yearly Fluctuations:** Both entities observed 2016 as a standout year in terms of project submissions and competitions, yet the underlying reasons for this surge may vary.
7. **Gender and Competitive Landscape:** The competitive dynamics, in terms of research competitions, showcase potential gender influences, especially in public universities.
8. **Resilience and Adaptability:** Despite gender disparities in certain areas, both entities showcase resilience in navigating challenges, as evidenced by recovery trends post

Figure 27. Second awareness session at UEFISCDI

3.7.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

This meeting, held on **Wednesday November 8, 2023** with UEFISCDI employees, focused on outlining and discussing the future actions for the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) 2024. The primary aim was to establish a clear roadmap for integrating gender equality and inclusiveness into research and innovation, enhancing expertise in gender-sensitive research evaluation, and promoting gender equality policies at the national level.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
10:00 – 10:10	Opening and welcome speech	<i>Alex Dinu</i>
10:10 – 11:10	Presentation of GEP 2024, each action was followed by Q&A	<i>Alex Dinu</i>
11:10 – 11:20	Feedback from audience	<i>All participants</i>

11:20 – 11:30

Conclusions and closing remarks

Alex Dinu

Participants

In total, 11 participants attended the session, 7 of whom were females and 4 males. Two participants represented high/top management functions.

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The session commenced with an overview of the GEP 2024 objectives, emphasizing the need for comprehensive guidelines to integrate gender dimensions in research. The discussion then moved to the dissemination of GA+ benchmark results, highlighting the importance of raising awareness and understanding within the Romanian research community.

Main outcomes and remarks

Subsequent talks focused on developing training modules for research evaluators and organizing workshops and webinars to enhance stakeholder knowledge on gender equality. The establishment of a zero-tolerance policy against gender-based violence within research and innovation activities was discussed, outlining the steps for policy development, implementation, and monitoring.

A significant part of the meeting was dedicated to the formation of a national task force for advancing gender equality policies in research and innovation. This task force aims to define objectives, appoint members, develop strategic plans, and collaborate with national authorities.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered.

Conclusion

The session concluded with a discussion on the outlined actions, emphasizing the ongoing commitment of UEFISCDI to promote gender equality in research and innovation.

Supporting material

o establish guidelines for incorporating the gender dimension into research content, ensuring gender equality and inclusiveness in research and innovation.	Develop comprehensive guidelines that provide clear instructions on integrating the gender dimension into research content, including project design, implementation, and evaluation	Process: Number of drafts and revisions of the guidelines. Impact: Adoption and usage of the guidelines by research institutions and projects.	Researchers Research Funding Organizations Research Performing Organizations Policy makers Research project teams	Policy briefs Guidance documents	4	Y	N	UEFISCDI (Romanian Funding Organization)	ongoing
o disseminate and promote benchmark results on GA+ within the Romanian research community.	Organize dedicated events to present benchmark results. Publish articles and reports highlighting the key findings and implications. Collaborate with relevant research organizations and institutions for wider outreach. Engage with local stakeholders for broader dissemination.	Process: Number of seminars, workshops, and conferences conducted. Impact: Increase in the awareness and understanding of benchmark results within the research community.	Researchers Research Funding Organizations Research Performing Organizations Policy makers Media General public	Benchmarking, policy briefs, baseline document, guidance	2,3,4,5,6	Y	N	UEFISCDI (Romanian Funding Organization)	ongoing
o enhance the expertise of research evaluators in understanding and applying gender equality principles in research assessment.	Develop training modules on gender equality in research evaluation. Conduct training sessions for research evaluators. Create online resources for continuous learning. Establish a certification program for trained evaluators. Monitor and assess the impact of training on evaluation processes.	Process: Number of training sessions conducted. Impact: Improvement in gender-sensitive research evaluation practices.	Research Evaluators Research Funding Organizations Research Performing Organizations Universities and Research Institutions	Policy report, strategic policy advice, benchmarking	2,3,4,5,6	Y	N	UEFISCDI (Romanian Funding Organization)	ongoing
o enhance the knowledge and capacity of stakeholders in promoting gender equality in research and innovation.	Organize workshops, webinars, and training sessions on gender equality topics. Develop resource materials and toolkits for stakeholders. Facilitate knowledge sharing and networking opportunities. Establish a community of practice for ongoing support. Monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of capacity building activities.	Process: Number of capacity building activities conducted. Impact: Increased gender equality awareness and capacity among stakeholders.	Policy makers Research Funding Organizations Research Performing Organizations NGOs Civil Society Organizations	Benchmarking, policy briefs, baseline document, guidance	3,6,7	Y	Y	UEFISCDI (Romanian Funding Organization)	ongoing
o establish and enforce a zero-tolerance policy against gender-based violence within research and innovation activities.	Develop a clear and comprehensive zero-tolerance policy. Implement procedures for reporting and addressing gender-based violence incidents. Provide training and awareness programs for staff and stakeholders. Monitor and review the effectiveness of the policy regularly. Publish annual reports on the outcomes and actions taken.	Process: Number of incidents reported and addressed. Impact: Reduction in gender-based violence incidents and improved reporting mechanisms.	Researchers Universities Research Funding Organizations Research Performing Organizations Research Project Teams	Benchmarking, strategic policy advice, policy briefs,				FLIA CENTER	

Figure 28. Third awareness raising session at UEFISCDI – GEP actions overview

3.8 Yasar University (YU)

3.8.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The second awareness session at Yasar University aimed to summarize the first implementation process of the institutional gender equality plan and strategize improvements, identify and resolve any possible resistances or obstacles, and receive feedback from the internal experts, academics and managers who are involved in the GEP implementation at Yasar University. The event was organized **on 28 November 2022** as a face-to-face meeting in Izmir, Turkey.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
10:00-10:15	Opening and welcome speech	<i>Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i>
	Presentation of CALIPER Project & GEP	<i>Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator</i>
10:15-10:45	Discussion	<i>GEP Working Group Members, Top Level Managers, Middle Level Managers</i>
10:45-11:00	Conclusion & Remarks	<i>Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i>
		<i>Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator</i>

Participants

In total, 18 participants attended the session, with a ratio of 11 female to 7 male participants. The participants were all academic representatives from YU and the composition included 10 academics (6 Prof., 3 Assoc.Prof.Dr, and 1 Lecturer), 8 administrative representatives (1 deputy secretary general, 1 director, 6 experts from human resources and EU research center), 4 executives from high/top management (2 Vice Rectors, 1 Dean, 1 Deputy Secretary General) and 7 individuals from middle management positions (5 Directors of research centers/central academic planning & quality unit/competition relations analysis and central planning; and 2 Heads of departments).

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The CALIPER project team at YU planned the second round of awareness session with the involvement and participation of GEP working group, high-level management and academics on 28 November 2022 as a face-to-face event to increase the interaction between participants and promote the successful implementation of GEP in the first itinerary. The method used during the session was an **open discussion method** facilitated by the institutional project coordinator and assistant project coordinator.

The CALIPER team presented the completed, ongoing and planned activities within the institutional GEP and for each priority area. The group reflected on the facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation process and suggested improvements to the implementation process.

Main outcomes and remarks

Participants emphasized the role that CALIPER project played in **the acceleration of gender equality as a priority strategy for the university for the last 3 years**. According to the deputy secretary general and director of human resources at YU, top management has always been interested and paid attention to gender equality, but it was the CALIPER project and GEP implementation that created structured and targeted measures as well as institutional organs that are responsible for monitoring the issue at the university. Therefore, **the institutional mechanisms established at the beginning of the process have been the main triggering factor and facilitating element in GEP implementation**.

According to the Vice Rector, Research and Innovation, **the institutional culture and the top management ownership** have been facilitating factors for the successful implementation GEP. With this support, gender research center was established quickly. Prior to GEP implementation, there was no mechanism for sexual harassment and it was largely an ignored issue. CALIPER GEP provided legal background and a responsible unit for sexual harassment complaints. This increases **institutional accountability and legal protection** for students and staff members. Furthermore, through training and awareness raising activities, researchers have become more interested in gender equality. There have been other project applications specifically for STEM area in the last year, **creating a multiplier effect**.

The group highlighted **the lack of awareness or gender blindness** as hindering factors in the engagement of some staff members in activities. More training opportunities and awareness raising activities are seen to be solutions for this obstacle.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered.

Conclusion

The participants became aware of the importance of GEP Working Group for collaborative work across GEP action areas. Institutional transformation and high-level ownership have been commonly highlighted as catalysing factors for the success of GEP.

Supporting material

Figure 29. Second awareness session at YU

CALIPER PROJESİ
CİNSİYET EŞİTLİĞİ İÇİN ARAŞTIRMA VE YENİLİKÇİLİK

CALIPER projesi, ortak kurumlarda Toplumsal Cinsiyet Planları'nın (GEP) geliştirilmesi ve uygulanması yoluyla akademide ve araştırma kuruluşlarında toplumsal cinsiyet eşitliğine ilişkin farkındalığı ve cinsiyet eşitliğini arttırmayı hedeflemektedir.

Projemiz özellikle 'Fen Bilimleri, Teknoloji, Mühendislik ve Matematik' (STEM) disiplinlerinde, kadınların akademik pozisyonlardaki payını arttırmayı, karar verme ve araştırmaya ilişkin süreçlerde cinsiyet dengesini sağlamayı amaçlamaktadır.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

Yaşar Üniversitesi Cinsiyet Eşitliği Planı

ÖNCELİK ALANLARI

6. CİNSEL TACİZ
• Cinsiyete Dayalı/Cinsel Taciz

5. KURUMSAL İLETİŞİM
• Cinsiyete Duyarlı Kurumsal İletişim

4. EĞİTİM-ÖĞRETİM
• Cinsiyete Duyarlı Öğretim

3. ARAŞTIRMA
• Araştırma İçerik ve Yöntemleri

2. KURUMSAL YÖNETİŞİM
• Cinsiyet Eşitliği Politikaları ve Organları
• Karar verme süreçlerinde cinsiyet dengesi

1. İNSAN KAYNAKLARI
• İşe Alım ve Seçme
• Karıyer Gelişimi

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

Figure 30. Second awareness session at YU – Snapshots from session's presentation

3.8.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The third awareness session at Yasar University was organized on **11 May 2023** with the participation of internal experts, academics, managers and students. The session aimed to discuss and review the implemented GEP actions and the actions which are currently being implemented.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
------	----------	------------

13:00 – 13:15	Opening and welcome speech	<i>Prof.Dr.Mehmet Cemali DİNÇER, Rector, Yaşar University</i>
13:15 – 14:15	Presentation of GEP and the GEP process	<i>Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i>
14:15 – 15:00	Open round discussion on actions and feedback	<i>Internal stakeholders and CALIPER team</i>
15:00 – 15:15	Conclusion & Remarks	<i>Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i>

Participants

In total, 30 persons participated, 18 of whom were female and 12 were male. In terms of composition, 15 participants were students, while 7 were academicians (3 Professors, 2 Associate Professors and 2 Assistant Professors) and 6 participants came from administrative positions (1 Director, 2 Chiefs, 2 Experts and 1 project Assistant). In addition, 2 external managers took part, from 1 RPO and 1 RFO. Out of the total participants, 2 of them represented high/top management positions, that is, 1 Rector and 1 Dean of Faculty of Humanities.

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

CALIPER project team at YU planned the third round of awareness session with the involvement and participation of internal experts, academics, managers and students on 11 May 2023 to discuss and inform the internal stakeholders on the implementation of the institutional Gender Equality Plan (GEP). The workshop also aimed to increase the internal understanding of the plan's objectives and measures to improve gender equality at the Yaşar University.

The session gave participants a forum to learn more about the GEP actions, express their opinions, address questions and actively participate in the GEP's effective implementation through interesting presentations and open discussions. Different from the first two rounds, students of *Diversity Studies* course also participated in the session which contributed to the diversity dimension of the GEP.

Minutes per thematic area

The University Rector, Prof.Dr.Mehmet Cemali Dinçer, opened the session with a speech on the importance of institutionalization of gender equality through CALIPER project. CALIPER project coordinator Prof.Dr.Gökay Özerim presented the completed, ongoing and planned activities within the institutional GEP and for each priority area. The group reflected on the facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation process and suggested improvements.

Speakers addressed the role of the CALIPER project in bringing gender equality as a priority strategy, objective and policy for the institution in different areas such as human resources, institutional governance, research, teaching-training, institutional communication and prevention of sexual harassment. Top and middle management stressed that structural and targeted measures in the GEP implementation provide sustainability of gender equality in the organization.

In addition, there were two external stakeholders in the meeting. A program expert from Turkish National Agency (RFO responsible for the implementation of EU education, training and youth programmes) and a project manager from Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (on Erasmus+ Staff Mobility Exchange visiting YU

European Union Research Centre). Their participation in the session provided an opportunity to have an external perspective on YU GEP and a space to exchange good practices.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered. The meeting was fruitful and productive.

Conclusion

Similar to the previous awareness raising sessions, the participants stressed the importance of a GEP working group for collaborative work across GEP action areas. In addition, institutional transformation and high-level ownership were seen as facilitating factors for the success of a GEP. According to the top and middle-level management, sustainability of the GEP actions will be ensured through a careful planning and institutionalization process.

Supporting material

Figure 31. Third awareness raising session at YU – Welcome speech

Figure 32. Third awareness raising session at YU – GEP updates

Figure 33. Third awareness raising session at YU – Group photo

3.9 University of Salento (UNILE)

3.9.1 Second awareness raising session

Introduction

The event was held on the **29 of March 2022** and was focused on the planning of orientation activities on gender issues: the events to be performed during the inbound orientation activities for choosing university

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

courses (opening days and dissemination seminars in schools) with an enlarged working group that involved the Rector, the Delegate for Orientation, the Delegate for Equal Opportunities, the reference person for orientation of the Department of Mathematics, the experts for orientation of the University of Salento, the Presidents of the degree courses and some school managers.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
11:00 – 11:20	Opening and introduction of the event	<i>Anna Maria Cherubini- Delegate for Gender Policies</i>
11:20 – 11:30	Welcome speech	<i>Fabio Pollice-Rector of University of Salento</i>
11:30 – 11:50	Presentation of UniSalento CARE: educational offer and gender policy	<i>Prof. Attilio Pisanò - Vice Rector for University courses implementation</i>
11:50 – 12:20	Discussion on ORIENTATION AND COUNSELING@ Unisalento in a GEP perspective	<i>Prof. Emanuela Ingusci – Vice Rector for ORIENTATION AND COUNSELING</i>
12:20 – 12:30	Conclusion	<i>Anna Maria Cherubini- Delegate for Gender Policies</i>

Participants

In total, 30 persons took part in the event, with a female-to-male ratio at 20 female participants to 10 male ones. In terms of participants' representation, 25 of them came from the University and 5 of them from civil society and they represented high/top management positions in their organisations. The event was attended by the UNILE Rector, members of CORT ([Come Scegliere - UNISALENTO CARE - Università del Salento](#)), Vice-Rector for Gender Policies and University Professors.

The WG that was involved consisted of the GEP coordination and monitoring group members, the Rector, the Delegate for Orientation, the vice-Rector for Equal Opportunities, the reference person for orientation of the Department of Mathematics, the experts for orientation of the University of Salento, the Presidents of the degree courses and some school managers.

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The scope of this meeting was to plan the organisation of special events or dedicated stands for the activities of the UNISALENTO CARE (Iniziativa Speciali - UNISALENTO CARE - Università del Salento), which is in charge of all the activities concerning student orientation and tutoring.

The need to involve all the components of the University in the implementation of the GEP and the importance of the goal achieved, that is the approval of the first GEP of UNILE, has led the Institutional Bodies to consider indispensable the wide-spread sharing of the plan for activities aimed at increasing the presence of women in university courses, especially in STEM disciplines. This consensus among the session's participants was recognised as an essential step in order to obtain the commitment of the resources that are required to sustain the motivation and perseverance of the process of GEP actions and measures implementation.

Main outcomes

The main outcomes were the organization of some seminars and open days in scientific laboratories and/or departments (see images below). All the events were decided to be held in person, most in individual departments and follow a more practical-laboratory character. There was a consensus to organise face-to-face open discussions, supported by presentations or storytelling in order to increase awareness and engagement. It has been also agreed that in all the events some specific presentation to be given by female professors and female PhD students or students representative, with the aim to engage more girls.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered.

Supporting material

Figure 34. Second awareness raising session at UNILE – planned orientation activities 1/2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 35. Second awareness raising session at UNILE – planned orientation activities 2/2

3.9.2 Third awareness raising session

Introduction

The event was linked with the inauguration ceremony of “PROTAGONISTE- November of UniSalento against violence” which took place on **14 November 2022** at MuSA (Museo storico-archeologico dell’Università del Salento). The main theme of the event was the presentation of initiatives organized by UNILE, which were realized during November and December of 2022, for contrasting gender violence, promoting non-discriminating communication, and including gender dimension in research. In this context, this meeting was a great opportunity to showcase the role of the CALIPER project for the realization of UNILE’s GEP.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s)
11:00 – 11:20	Opening and introduction of the event	Anna Maria Cherubini - Delegate for Gender Policies
11:20 – 11:30	Welcome speech	Fabio Pollice-Rector of UNILE
11:30 – 11:50	Presentation of UNILE GEP	Monica McBritton-CUG President
11:50 – 12:20	Discussion on women’s philosophy ideology	Elena Laurenzi, Researcher of UNILE
12:20 – 12:30	Conclusion	Anna Maria Cherubini- Delegate for Gender Policies

Participants

In total the event was attended by 60 participants, out of whom 40 were female and 20 were male.. In regard to the stakeholders representation, 40 participants came from Academia and 20 from civil society

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organisations. Higher/top management representatives took part in the event, including a Rector, the CUG President, the Delegate for Gender Policies and several University Professors.

Minutes

Scope & Methodology

The scope of this meeting was to present all the activities involved in "PROTAGONISTE - November of UniSalento against violence ", a cycle of initiatives organized by the University of Salento to analyze gender-based violence giving space and visibility to the strength and intelligence of women who undertake resistance actions of circumvention and contrast. Theatre, cinema, photography, video-documentary and historical narrative are the languages chosen to address the theme, with the intention of denouncing the violence that derives from information campaigns exclusively centered on the figure of the victim and instead putting women at the center as protagonists in private and public life. PROTAGONISTE was promoted by the Delegate for Gender Policies, Anna Maria Cherubini, and by the CUG President, Monica Mc Britton, based on a design idea of Elena Laurenzi and with the collaboration of Paola Martino and Grazia Maria SignoreMinutes per thematic area.

Moreover, CUG President talked about the UNILE GEP underlying the importance of the Gender Equality Plan for all the different academic institutions and for students. The importance of the CALIPER project to sustain the several activities involved in the UNILE GEP was explained by the Delegate for Gender Policies.

Resistances

No internal resistances were encountered. The meeting was fruitful and productive.

Conclusion

The main outcomes of PROTAGINISTE consisted on promoting awareness events to academic people and civil society for contrasting gender violence, discriminating communication, and for including gender dimension in research, demonstrating that violence against women is not a women's issue, but concerns the whole community.

Supporting material

A press release in the UNILE's official web portal can be found in the following [link](#).

The complete guide of the UNILE's event can be accessed via this [link](#), while a shared folder with photos of the event can be accessed via this [link](#).

UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO
Cultura è vita. Da due anni!

g gruppo di lavoro

EOS Equal Opportunity UniSalento

CALIPER Centro Nazionale per la Ricerca in Psicologia e Scienze Umane

PROTAGONISTE

Il novembre di UniSalento contro la violenza

INAUGURAZIONE
14 novembre 2022, ore 11.00
MUSA, Museo storico-archeologico dell'Università del Salento
Complesso Stadium 2000, via di Valerio, Lecce

Intervengono:
Fabio Pollice, Rettore dell'Università del Salento
Anna Maria Cherubini, Delegata alle Politiche di genere, Università del Salento
Monica Mc Britton, Presidente del CUG, Università del Salento
Elena Laurenzi, Università del Salento

MOSTRA
"Spazi vissuti, spazi conquistati" di Pia Ranzano
14 novembre – 15 dicembre 2022
MUSA, Museo storico-archeologico dell'Università del Salento
Complesso Stadium 2000, via di Valerio, Lecce
Inaugurazione 14 novembre ore 11.30, alla presenza dell'artista

SEMINARIO
"Per non essere mai più sole"
15 novembre 2022, ore 17.30
Aula 7 edificio 3
Complesso Stadium 2000, via di Valerio, Lecce
Presentazione del libro di Nadia Maria Filippini "Mai più sole!" Contro la violenza sessuale. Una pagina storica del femminismo negli anni Settanta, Vellea, 2022
Racconto di Nadia Maria Filippini, S.I.S. Società Italiana delle Storiche, già Università Ca' Foscari con proiezioni di immagini e video inediti
lettura scenica a cura delle studentesse e degli studenti del DAVES
Moderata: Elena Laurenzi
Saluti: Mariano Longo, Direttore del Dipartimento di Scienze umane e sociali

PROIEZIONE DEL FILM DOCUMENTARIO
"Ma l'amore c'entra?" di Elisabetta Lodoli
22 novembre 2022, ore 17.00
UniSalento Community Library
Edificio MAUS Complesso Ecotekne, via per Monteson, Lecce
Introduce: Monica Mc Britton, Presidente del CUG, Università del Salento
Ne discutono:
Stefano Ciccone, Associazione Maschile plurali
Maria Giuseppina Pacilli, Università di Perugia
Moderata: Terri Altanarini, Università del Salento

SPETTACOLO TEATRALE
"Doppio taglio. Come i media raccontano la violenza sulle donne" di Marina Senesi
23 novembre 2022, ore 19.30
Teatro Politeama Greco
Via XXV Luglio 30, Lecce
Introduce: Anna Maria Cherubini, Delegata alle Politiche di genere, Università del Salento
Al termine dello spettacolo **Marina Senesi** dialogherà con **Loredana De Vitis**, Giornalista, e con il pubblico

CINEFORUM
"Cambio di scena"
17 novembre – 6 dicembre 2022
D6 Dessai Cinema e Teatro
via Salesiani 4, Lecce
in collaborazione con Cineclub UniSalento e Progetto DB Giovani

17 novembre 2022, ore 18.30
Persepolis di Marjane Satrapi (2017)

24 novembre 2022, ore 18.30
Libere Disobbedienti Innamorate (in Betweem)
di Maysaloun Haroud (2016)

1 dicembre 2022, ore 18.30
Pane e tulipani
di Silvio Soldini (2000)

6 dicembre 2022, ore 18.30
La Bicicletta verde
di Hailoo Al-Marsouf (2012)

Attività a cura di
Anna Maria Cherubini,
Elena Laurenzi,
Monica Mc Britton,
Paola Maffei,
Daniela Maria Spascer.
L'idea progettuale di
Daniela Laurenzi

QUINTI **CINE CLUB** **DB Dessai** **S**

Figure 36. Third awareness raising session at UNILE – PROTAGONISTE agenda

FORMAZIONE E TERZA MISSIONE | "PROTAGONISTE": IL NOVEMBRE DI UNISALENTO CONTRO LA VIOLENZA DI GENERE

"Protagoniste. Il novembre di UniSalento contro la violenza" è il ciclo di iniziative organizzato dall'Università del Salento per analizzare la violenza di genere, nelle sue molteplici dimensioni e sfaccettature, dando spazio e visibilità alla forza e all'intelligenza delle donne che intraprendono azioni di resistenza, di aggiramento e di contrasto. Teatro, cinema, fotografia, video-documentario e racconto storico sono i linguaggi scelti per affrontare il tema, con l'intento di denunciare la violenza secondaria che deriva da campagne informative esclusivamente centrate sulla figura della vittima e mettere invece al centro le donne come protagoniste nella vita privata e in quella pubblica. Nel contesto delle iniziative promosse in tutto il mondo in occasione della Giornata internazionale per l'eliminazione della violenza contro le donne del 25 novembre, "Protagoniste" si pone in continuità con l'impegno in materia dell'Ateneo, che ha organizzato tra l'altro il corso di formazione "Violenza contro le donne: un approccio di genere".

nota e programma dell'iniziativa "Protagoniste" > https://www.unisalento.it/comunicati/-/asset_publisher/C6YX5RjDCSpB/content/dal-14-novembre-ciclo-di-iniziative-contro-violenza-di-genero

nota sul corso di formazione > https://www.unisalento.it/comunicati/-/asset_publisher/C6YX5RjDCSpB/content/20-settembre-lezione-magistrale-chiara-saraceno

video "no alla violenza sulle donne" > <https://youtu.be/GpiF4VA2WGw>

Figure 37. Third awareness raising session at UNILE – Press Release clip

3.10 Summary of the participants

This summary contains two tables:

1. The overall reach of the activities per partner and per event
2. The overall reach of different stakeholders (approximately)

In the table below, there is an overview of all the events, demonstrating the number of participants in the different events for each RPO/RFO.

Table 5. Overall attendance of the activities per partner and per event

Partner	Type of event		
	Awareness raising sessions	WIN event	Total
UZG – FER	32	-	32
SRNSFG	31	46*	57
STU BA	130**	-	
ULB	21	-	21
ECE – NTUA	22	-	22
IRB	63***	50	113
UEFISCDI	19	-	19
YU	48	-	48
UNILE	90****	-	90

*SRNSFG had already implemented the assigned WIN event in 2022

**STU BA organised its second awareness raising session jointly with its internal WG workshop as well as its WIN event

***IRB held its third awareness raising session in two parts, one internal and one external

****UNILE hosted its third awareness raising session in the context of a university-wide event

The table below summarises an indicative count of the stakeholder types reached through the activities per partner (approximately).

Table 6. Summary of the types of stakeholder attracted by the RPOs/RFOs

Partner	Type of stakeholders					
	Internal staff	Academia	Students	Business Industry	Government Sector	Civil Society
UZG – FER	15	4	-	3	2	-
SRNSFG	38	15	-	1	19	1
STU BA	65	35	11	12	7	-
ULB	5	14	2	-	-	-
ECE – NTUA	14	8	-	-	-	-
IRB	12	71	17	10	3	-
UEFISCDI	19	-	-	-	-	-
YU	14	17	15	1	1	-
UNILE	-	65	-	-	-	25
Total	182	229	45	27	21	26

4 Conclusion

The current deliverable concludes the reporting and documentation of the engagement activities of each GEP implementing RPO and RFO of the project. These activities were organised in the context of *T5.3 - Raising awareness and engagement activities* with links and interdependencies with *T5.2 - Engaging with the innovation ecosystems* as well as *T6.2 - Intra-institutional internal communication*.

Through these events, the CALIPER RPOs and RFOs had the opportunity to engage internal and external stakeholders with their GEP actions. Continuing from D5.3, the first version of this report, the current deliverable presents the RPOs/RFOs efforts to engage with internal bodies and individuals across all managerial levels to deepen the internal gender equality culture and bring institutional change. What is more, D5.6 provides adequate reporting regarding the remaining external/outwards activities for the engagement of the R&I Hubs that the RPOs/RFOs have created in the context of the project, with stakeholders from the local and national ecosystems are an attempt to influence using the project's results other academic institutions/organisations, or industry players, to adopt gender equal policies and structure their own GEP.

